

Production of intracellular microbial oils (MOs) using oleaginous yeasts, from hydrolysates of lignocellulosic materials

Ricardo Rafael Antunes Francisco

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Supervisors:

Dr. Maria Teresa Saraiva Lopes da Silva

Prof. José António Leonardo dos Santos

Examination Committee

Chairperson: Prof. Gabriel António Amaro Monteiro

Supervisor: Dr. Maria Teresa Saraiva Lopes da Silva

Members of the Committee: Prof. Maria Teresa Ferreira Cesário Smolders

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Preface

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All the work mentioned in this document took place at the Bioenergy and Biorefineries Research Unit of the Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia (LNEG), located in Lisbon (Portugal), between September 2022 and March 2023, under the local supervision of Dr. Maria Teresa Saraiva Lopes da Silva.

The writing of this document was supervised by Dr. Maria Teresa Saraiva Lopes da Silva and co-supervised by Prof. José António Leonardo dos Santos, assistant professor at the Department of Bioengineering (area of Biomolecular and Bioprocess Engineering) of the Instituto Superior Técnico (IST), located in Lisbon (Portugal).

I declare that this document is an original work of my own authorship and that it fulfils all the requirements of the Code of Conduct and Good Practices of the Universidade de Lisboa (UL).

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Resumo

Em consonância com uma visão de economia circular, foram estudadas três estirpes de leveduras oleaginosas, designadamente, das espécies *Rhodotorula babjevae*, *Trichosporon oleaginosus* e *Rhodotorula toruloides*, quanto ao seu potencial de valorização de hidrolisados de palha de milho (HPM) através da produção de óleos intracelulares microbianos (OMs). A estirpe de melhor desempenho, em termos de produção de lípidos, foi selecionada para posterior otimização e escalonamento do bioprocessamento.

Preliminarmente, as três leveduras promissoras foram cultivadas em balões agitados de 1 L, contendo 150 mL de meio sintético cuja composição simulava a composição do HPM. As *R. toruloides* e *T. oleaginosus* destacaram-se apresentando produtividades volumétricas globais em lípidos de 0.081 ± 0.009 g_L/L/h e 0.119 ± 0.001 g_L/L/h, o correspondente aos títulos de lípidos de 7.7 ± 0.9 g_L/L e 8.4 ± 0.1 g_L/L, respetivamente. Analogamente, as mesmas foram cultivadas em HPM real, evidenciando-se, uma vez mais, a *T. oleaginosus* com uma produtividade volumétrica global e um título de lípidos de 0.144 ± 0.004 g_L/L/h e 6.8 ± 0.2 g_L/L, correspondentemente.

Uma vez eleita, a *T. oleaginosus* foi cultivada em 2 L de meio sintético simulando a composição do HPM, em regime semi-descontínuo com adição de um pulso de carbono, tendo resultado numa produtividade volumétrica global em lípidos de 0.018 ± 0.003 g_L/L/h, possivelmente devido a limitações ao fornecimento de oxigénio e ao fenómeno de formação de espuma. Paralelamente, utilizou-se a técnica de citometria de fluxo (CF) associada a um método de dupla coloração com iodeto de propídio (IP) e verde SYBR I (VSI), para deteção da integridade da membrana.

Palavras-chave: Óleos Microbianos; *Rhodotorula toruloides*; *Rhodotorula babjevae*; *Trichosporon oleaginosus*; Hidrolisados de Palha de Milho; Citometria de Fluxo.

Abstract

Towards a circular economy, three oleaginous yeast strains, namely, from *Rhodotorula babjevae*, *Trichosporon oleaginosus* and *Rhodotorula toruloides* species were studied due to their potential to valorise corn stover hydrolysates (CSH) through the production of intracellular microbial oils (MOs). The best performing strain, in terms of lipid production, was selected for further bioprocess optimization and scale-up.

Preliminarily, the three promising yeasts were cultivated in 1 L-Erlenmeyer flasks, containing 150 mL of synthetic medium simulating the composition of CSH. The yeasts *R. toruloides* and *T. oleaginosus* stood out with global lipid volumetric productivities of 0.081 ± 0.009 g_L/L/h and 0.119 ± 0.001 g_L/L/h, with corresponding lipid titres of 7.7 ± 0.9 g_L/L and 8.4 ± 0.1 g_L/L, respectively. By analogy, the same yeasts were cultivated on real CSH, emphasizing once more *T. oleaginosus* with a global volumetric productivity and lipid titre of 0.144 ± 0.004 g_L/L/h and 6.8 ± 0.2 g_L/L, correspondingly.

Once selected, *T. oleaginosus* was cultured in a 7 L-bioreactor containing 2 L of CSH-mimic synthetic medium, under fed-batch mode with the addition of a carbon pulse, resulting in a global volumetric lipid productivity of 0.018 ± 0.003 g_L/L/h, most likely due to oxygen limitation and foaming phenomena. In parallel, Flow Cytometry (FC) technique was used together with a propidium iodide (PI) and SYBR green I (SGI) double-staining method for membrane integrity detection.

Keywords: Microbial Oils; *Rhodotorula toruloides*; *Rhodotorula babjevae*; *Trichosporon oleaginosus*; Corn Stover Hydrolysates; Flow Cytometry.

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Abbreviations

5-HMF acid	5-(hydroxymethyl)-2-furoic acid
5-HMF alcohol	5-(hydroxymethyl)-2-furfuryl alcohol
Acetyl-CoA	Acetyl coenzyme A
ACL	ATP-citrate lyase
AMP	Adenosine monophosphate
ATP	Adenosine triphosphate
BE	Belgium
C 14:0	Tetradecanoic acid
C 16:0	Palmitic acid
C 16:1 ω-7	Palmitoleic acid
C 17:1 ω-7	Heptadecenoic acid
C 18:0	Stearic acid
C 18:1 ω-9	Oleic acid
C 18:2 ω-6	Linoleic acid
C 18:3 ω-3	α -linolenic acid
C 18:3 ω-6	γ -linolenic acid
C 24:0	Lignoceric acid
C:N	Carbon to nitrogen molar ratio
C:P	Carbon to phosphorus molar ratio
C:S	Carbon to sulphur molar ratio
CFH	Cellulose fibre hydrolysate
CH	Switzerland
CMT	Citrate-malate translocase
CS	Corn stover
CSL	Corn steep liquor
CSH	Corn stover hydrolysate
CSS	Circular systemic solutions
DAD	Diode-array detector
DCW	Dry cell weight
DE	Germany
DHA	Docosahexaenoic acid
DK	Denmark
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid

DO	Dissolved oxygen
EPA	Eicosapentaenoic acid
ER	Endoplasmic reticulum
FA	Fatty acid
FAO	Food and agriculture organization of the United Nations
FC	Flow cytometry
FID-GC	Gas Chromatography with Flame Ionization Detection
FR	France
FSC	Front scatter
GHG	Greenhouse gas
HMF	5-(hydroxymethyl)-2-furfural
HPLC	High-performance liquid chromatography
IDH	Isocitrate dehydrogenase
IMO	Inosine monophosphate
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IST	Instituto Superior Técnico
JP	Japan
L	Lipid
LB	Lipid body
LUC	Land use change
MCT	Monocarboxylic acid transporter
MDH	Malate dehydrogenase
MEA	Malt extract agar
MUFA	Monounsaturated fatty acid
MW	Molecular weight
NADPH	Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate
OD	Optical density
OTR	Oxygen transfer rate
OUR	Oxygen uptake rate
PBS	Phosphate-buffered saline
PD	Photodiode detector
PDH	Pyruvate dehydrogenase
PEFA	Polyol esters of fatty acids
PEG	Polyethylene glycol
PI	Propidium iodide
PID	Proportional-Integral-Derivative
PMT	Photomultiplier tubes

PPG	Polypropylene glycol
PT	Portugal
PTFE	Polytetrafluoroethylene
PU	Polyurethane
PUFA	Polyunsaturated fatty acid
RID	Refractive index detector
RNA	Ribonucleic acid
ROS	Reactive oxygen species
rpm	Rotations per minute
SFA	Saturated fatty acid
SGI	SYBR Green I
SSC	Side Scatter
SSP	Shared socio-economic pathways
STEX	Steam explosion
STR	Stirred-tank reactor
TKN	Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen
UK	United Kingdom
USA	United States of America
vvm	Volume of air per volume of culture medium per minute
WCO	Waste cooking oils
WSH	Wheat straw hydrolysate
YNB	Yeast nitrogen base
YPD	Yeast extract peptone and dextrose

1. Introduction

1.1. Environmental emergency

Global warming, pollution, shortage of natural resources and loss of biodiversity in ecosystems represent some of the greatest concerns in human history. Since the pre-industrial era¹ the earth planet has experienced an increase in its global average surface temperature of about 0.99 °C (0.84 to 1.10 °C), or an even higher value of 1.59 °C (1.34 to 1.83 °C) if it refers only to land, as an undeniable result of greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions, namely, CO₂, CH₄ or N₂O, according to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2023). In particular, net GHG emissions are estimated to have reached 54.59 GtCO₂-eq² in 2021, of which quite close to the peak of 54.82 GtCO₂-eq² recorded in 2019 (Jones, et al., 2023).

Considering the cumulative effect of anthropogenic carbon emissions over the years, several scenarios for the global average surface temperature anomaly have been outlined based on Shared Socio-economic Pathways (SSP) in a time horizon until the beginning of the next century (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. Current profile and future SSP-based projections for global average surface temperature increase relative to values over the pre-industrial era (1850-1900): SSP1-2.6 (low GHG emissions), SSP2-4.5 (intermediate GHG emissions) and SSP3-8.5 (very high GHG emissions). Adapted from ClimateData.ca (2023).

According to a more optimistic scenario (SSP1-2.6), in which by 2070 CO₂ emissions reach net-zero, an increase of less than 2 °C is expected in 2100, while doubling GHG emissions by 2050 (SSP5-8.5), a dramatic warming of more than 4 °C is likely in the same year. Terribly, if CO₂ emissions are maintained at current values for the coming years (SSP2-4.5), a warming of around 3 °C is deduced in 2100. Nevertheless, only reaching net-zero

¹ Relative to 1850 – 1900 values.

² These values comprise CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O combined emissions from all sources, including agriculture and land use change (LUC), in terms of CO₂ equivalents, considering a Global Warming Potential for 100 years (GWP100).

CO₂ emissions in 2050 (SSP1-1.9), it will be possible to limit global warming to 1.5 °C, in line with the Paris Agreement of 2015 (IPCC, 2023; The Paris Agreement, 2015).

If, numerically, these forecasts are not enough to alarm human society, perhaps its harmful impacts could be, namely, the intensification of hurricane and tornado formation, the change in precipitation patterns, which is associated with severe drought or flooding episodes, the increase in frequency and severity of wildfires and heatwaves, the rise in the global sea level due to the glacier retreat, or species extinction (Alimonti, Mariani, Prodi, & Ricci, 2022; AghaKouchak, et al., 2020; Shivanna, 2020). As integral elements of the biosphere, human beings will also suffer the consequences of a climatically unstable earth, facing energy, food, water, or health issues accompanied by socio-economic imbalances in the next decades (Fawzy, Osman, Doran, & Rooney, 2020).

Considering that the efforts made until today are far from being sufficient to meet the goals of the Paris Agreement, which supposes in 2030 an ambitious reduction of 43 % and 48 % of GHG and CO₂ emissions (IPCC, 2023), respectively, humanity is inevitably condemned not only to adapt to the occurrence of extreme weather phenomena, but also to find short-term solutions to mitigate the damage inherent to this conjuncture, namely, by implementing strategies and technologies that allow the reduction in positive GHG emissions and also its capture and storage/utilisation, termed negative GHG emissions (Fawzy, Osman, Doran, & Rooney, 2020; IPCC, 2023). Among the various required actions, stand out the reconversion of the energy sector, improvements in the management of natural resources and waste, the reconversion of infrastructures and industry, or the implementation of a circular economy (Papadis & Tsatsaronis, 2020; Raj, Jhariya, Yadav, & Banerjee, 2020; Kätelhön, Meys, Deutz, Suh, & Bardow, 2019; Allard, 2021; Gallego-Schmid, Chen, Sharmina, & Mendoza, 2020). However, it should be stated that although it is a global trouble, its consequences may affect different regions of the globe in very diverse ways, requiring locally adjusted responses and efforts (Atwoli, et al., 2022).

Circular economy is defined as a commercial model according to which the term "waste" is replaced by the term "by-product", in a paradigm of minimising material and energy inputs, extending lifetime of overall resources, regenerating nature, as well as eliminating wastes and emissions (Circle Economy, 2022). Recently, the European Commission adopted the new Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP), a flagship action of the European Green Deal (European Commission, 2020). According to the 2022 Circularity Gap Report, it is estimated that only 8.6 % of the 100.6 Gt total resources entered in global economy in this year were recirculated, an even worst scenario than the 9.1 % recorded in 2020 (Circle Economy, 2022), which indicates that the linear economy still prevails and the efforts made so far are unsatisfactory.

It was in this regard that the European project FRONTSH1P raised, focusing on decarbonisation and territorial regeneration of the Łódzkie region in Poland, with four main Circular Systemic Solutions (CSS): Wood Packaging, Food and Feed, Water and Nutrients, and Plastics and Rubber Waste (FRONTSH1P, 2022).

1.2. Corn stover (CS): waste or by-product?

CS is a lignocellulosic material consisting essentially of stalks, leaves, and husks left over from the maize harvest, with a typical w/w composition of 35 % cellulose, 20 % hemicellulose and 12 % lignin (Ruan & Liao, 2019). It is estimated that between 2022 and 2023 around 1,151.36 Mt of maize have been produced worldwide, ranking first among the most important grains in the world, followed by wheat and rice (Shahbandeh, Worldwide production of grain in 2022/23, by type, 2023), and considering that about 50 % w/w of the maize plant corresponds to the stover fraction, also roughly 1.15 Gt of CS have been produced during the same period all over the globe (Ruan & Liao, 2019). Currently, the United States of America (USA) is the country with the highest share of maize crops with 348.75 Mt produced during the 2022-2023 period, followed by China and Brazil (Shahbandeh, Statista, 2023). Poland, particularly, presented a peak production of 6.7 Mt in 2020, as a result of an upward trend (Maize Production Trends, 2020), representing an opportunity to locally valorise the CS resulting from agricultural activity.

In general, lignocellulosic material consists of a well-organised structure in which cellulose fibrils are surrounded in a matrix of cross-linked hemicellulose, pectin, glycosylated proteins, and lignin, the latter being importantly associated with its recalcitrance (Auxenfans, Crônier, & Paës, 2017). Cellulose is a long-chain linear polymer constituted of repeated glucose residues linked through β -1,4-glycosidic bonds, which gives the CS its crystalline structure, and is susceptible to hydrolysis. Hemicellulose, on the other hand, is a matrix consisting of a wide range of polysaccharides composed by units such as xylose, mannose, arabinose, galactose, or glucuronic acid linked also through β -1,4-glycosidic bonds in the main chains and through β -1,2, β -1,3, and β -1,6-glycosidic bonds in the side chains, which surrounds cellulose and is also highly susceptible to hydrolysis. Finally, lignin is an amorphous non-linear macromolecule with phenylpropanoid derivatives as basic units linked through β -O-4 ether and C-C bonds, which gives the former structures support and rigidity. Typically, these three structures may establish hydrogen bonds and, particularly between lignin and hemicellulose, chemical bonds may also be established (Chen H. , 2014; Khan, Akbar, Xu, & Wang, 2021; Yu J. , 2009). Once monosaccharides like glucose or xylose are released from the CS via chemical or enzymatic hydrolysis, these can be biologically valorised to primary or secondary metabolic by-products such as alcohols or lipids, which in turn have applications including biofuels or bio-based materials (Lee & Alper, 2015; Qi & Liang, 2015).

Due to its recalcitrant sort, CS requires an appropriate pre-treatment prior to hydrolysis step, with the aim of breaking down the physical and chemical structure of the cell walls, allowing the maximisation of hydrolysis rates and yields (Yu J. , 2009; Khan, Akbar, Xu, & Wang, 2021). The CS pre-treatment methods currently known can be divided into four main categories: physical (e.g., mechanical extrusion, milling, ultrasonic or microwave irradiation, or pyrolysis), chemical (e.g., acidic, alkaline or with ionic liquids), biological (e.g., with brown-, white-, or soft-rot fungi), and also physicochemical (e.g., steam-explosion (STEX), hydrothermal treatment, ammonia fibre expansion, among others) (Khan, Akbar, Xu, & Wang, 2021). Indeed, STEX is one of the most

relevant pre-treatment methods for biomass rupture, which consists in the combined application of high pressures (from 0.7 to 5.0 MPa) and temperatures (from 160 to 260 °C), through the direct injection of saturated hot steam, for a short period of time (from 30 sec to 20 min), after which an explosive depressurization to atmospheric pressure is carried out, resulting in increased surface area of biomass, partial degradation and solubilisation of hemicellulose, increased accessibility of cellulose and redistribution of lignin (Keskin & Azbar, 2019; Auxenfans, Crônier, & Paës, 2017). This method can be also classified into acid-catalysed or non-catalysed, the latter being called autohydrolysis (Steinbach, Kruse, & Sauer, 2017). However, despite its high efficiency, low-cost, environmental sustainability and industrial scalability (Yu, et al., 2022; Khan, Akbar, Xu, & Wang, 2021), STEX also promotes the release of undesirable by-products such as short-chain organic acids (e.g., acetic, formic, or levulinic acids), sugar-derived aldehydes (e.g., 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF) or furfural), or aromatic compounds with emphasis on phenolic (e.g., ferulic acid, p-coumaric acid, hydroxycinnamic acid, hydrolysable tannin, vanillin, or syringaldehyde) (Steinbach, Kruse, & Sauer, 2017; Wan, et al., 2022; Sjulander & Kikas, 2020) (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2. Simplified scheme illustrating the processes that occur during non-catalysed STEX (autohydrolysis). Adapted from Sitepu, et al. (2014) and Minchin (2021).

The hydrolysis of the STEX pre-treated CS is essential for the depolymerisation of the remaining carbohydrates into their fermentable monomers, which can occur under acid catalysis, with diluted or concentrated acid, or under biocatalysis using hydrolytic enzymes such as β -glucosidase, endo- or exo-1,4- β -D-glucanase, among others (Machineni, 2019; Chen & Liu, 2017). At the outset, this latter method presents several advantages such as higher global productivities, lower energy requirements, lower water consumption or lower capital and operational costs, nevertheless, it also presents some limitations to industrial scalability, such as enzyme inhibition under high concentrations of monosaccharides, or water constraints and high viscosities under high solid concentrations (Chen & Liu, 2017). Enzymatic hydrolysis to CS pre-treated via STEX has been widely reported (Liu, Qin, Zhu, Li, & Yuan, 2014; Liu, Qin, Li, & Yuan, 2015).

1.2.1. Inhibitors: how can these compounds diminish the potential of CS?

The above-mentioned by-products, formed during STEX, are commonly associated with the inhibition not only of the microbial activity, but also of the enzymatic hydrolysis step itself, with consequent limitations on the global yields of biological valorisation processes (Sjulander & Kikas, 2020; Wang, Sun, & Yuan, 2018). However, the presence of inhibitors in the corn stover hydrolysates (CSH) is quite variable and depends on both the composition of the raw CS and the operating conditions promoted during STEX, namely pressure, temperature, pH, residence time, water content or the presence/absence of chemical catalysers. Particularly, pH values close to 7 or mild reaction conditions have been described to significantly reduce inhibitors formation (Sjulander & Kikas, 2020; Steinbach, Kruse, & Sauer, 2017). The toxicity of each inhibitor depends on multiple factors ranging from its concentration in the CSH, to the fermentation conditions such as pH or temperature, and also the tolerance mechanisms intrinsic to each microorganism (Sjulander & Kikas, 2020). In this sense, generic mechanisms of microbial inhibition by some of these compounds will be reviewed below.

1.2.1.1. Short-chain organic acids

Firstly, short-chain organic acids such as acetic or formic acids, when in their undissociated form – at pH values near or below their pK_a – cross cytoplasmic membranes by passive diffusion due to its lipophilicity, or through the Fps1p aquaglyceroporin channels in yeasts, ionizing and acidifying the intracellular medium (**Figure 3**) (Ndukwe, Aliyu, Onwosi, Chukwu, & Ezugworie, 2020; Palmqvist & Hahn-Hägerdal, 2000).

Figure 3. Simplified illustration of the generic mechanism of microbial inhibition by short-chain organic acids. Adapted from Hirshfield, Terzulli, & O'Byrne (2003).

Once inside the cells, their lipophobic conjugated bases (acetate, formate, etc.) cannot easily cross the membrane (Fernandes, Mira, Vargas, Canelhas, & Sá-Correia, 2005; Palmqvist & Hahn-Hägerdal, 2000), so they accumulate and induce adverse effects such as increased intracellular turgor pressure, oxidative stress, lipid peroxidation, protein aggregation, inhibition of membrane trafficking, inhibition of nucleic acid synthesis or disruption of the H⁺-ATPase pumps, the latter responsible for the acid-base cell homeostasis (Ndukwe, Aliyu, Onwosi, Chukwu, & Ezugworie, 2020). Additionally, due to their lipophilicity, these acids lead to organisational and functional membrane disruption in such a way that cells also become more vulnerable to H⁺ ion permeabilization with consequent breakdown of the electrochemical gradient that supports secondary active transport processes (Ndukwe, Aliyu, Onwosi, Chukwu, & Ezugworie, 2020). Thus, the acidity of the culture media, besides the effective concentration of these compounds, has a noticeable influence on the toxicity of short-chain organic acids, since for pH values close to or below their respective pK_a values the undissociated forms are present in more significant fractions, according to the Henderson–Hasselbalch equation (**Figure 4**). Moreover, the relative toxicity between the different acids has also been linked to their differences in membrane permeability (Palmqvist & Hahn-Hägerdal, 2000).

Figure 4. Molar distribution of the species acetic acid/acetate and formic acid/formate, by application of the Henderson–Hasselbalch equation, considering their respective pK_a values of 4.76 and 3.75 (Serjeant & B., 1979; Riddick, 1986).

However, some microorganisms possess innate mechanisms to respond to acid stress, e.g., the reconfiguration of the cell wall and plasma membrane, synthesis of intracellular proton pumps, activation of adaptive metabolic pathways, among them the accumulation of trehalose in the cytoplasm in yeasts (Ndukwe, Aliyu, Onwosi, Chukwu, & Ezugworie, 2020).

1.2.1.2. Sugar-derived aldehydes (the cases of HMF and furfural)

HMF and furfural are aromatic aldehyde compounds, also classified as furans, produced from the dehydration of hexoses and pentoses during STEEX, correspondingly, and their mechanism of toxicity is usually associated to the damage of DNA – which leads to protein synthesis inhibition –, injury of membranes, inhibition of the activity of dehydrogenases and glycolytic enzymes – having as a consequence the hinder of the Embden-Meyerhof-Parnas pathway reducing the ATP and NADPH availability –, or the destabilisation of redox metabolism with consequent accumulation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) contributing to oxidative stress issues. (Ask, Bettiga, Mapelli, & Olsson, 2013; Sjulander & Kikas, 2020; Wang, Brown, & Chen, 2018; Cheng, Shi, Li, Zong, & Li, 2020) In general, furfural presents more toxicity than HMF (Liu, et al., 2004; Wang, Q, & Bao, 2015;

Zou, Jin, Tao, Zheng, & Ouyang, 2022), which may be due to the lower membrane permeability of this latter (Palmqvist & Hahn-Hägerdal, 2000).

In return, some microorganisms also exhibit innate tolerance responses within certain limits, giving the example of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* which have shown the ability to anaerobically reduce HMF and furfural to their corresponding 5-hydroxymethyl furfuryl and furfuryl alcohols or aerobically oxidise them to 5-hydroxymethyl-2-furancarboxylic (5-HMF acid) and furoic acids, respectively (Ask, Bettiga, Mapelli, & Olsson, 2013; Zou, Jin, Tao, Zheng, & Ouyang, 2022). Although the metabolization of HMF and furfural is in general a detoxification mechanism, for other microorganisms these metabolites may even be more toxic compared to the primary molecules, considering the example of *Trichosporon fermentans* which shows more sensitivity to furfuryl alcohol than to furfural (Huang, et al., 2012).

1.2.1.3. Phenolic compounds

Phenolic compounds are among the most relevant lignin-derived inhibitors and their mechanism of inhibition is possibly due to their lipophilicity that allows them to accumulate in biological membranes and affect their respective integrity, with consequent loss of their selective barrier role. As such, growth and substrates uptake rates can be significantly affected. One of the molecular properties that can condition the relative toxicity between compounds is the molecular weight (MW), with lower MW compounds being considered more toxic. Additionally, these compounds can inhibit, or precipitate hydrolytic enzymes in the enzymatic hydrolysis step (Yu, Zeng, Zheng, & Chen, 2014; Zhao, Peng, Du, Liu, & Liu, 2012; Palmqvist & Hahn-Hägerdal, 2000; Sjulander & Kikas, 2020).

1.3. Biolubricants and bio-based polyurethanes (PUs): an opportunity for CS valorisation

Nowadays, lubricants and PU materials are widely present in everyday life, the former indispensable for most machinery and the latter with applications such as foams, coatings, insulations, adhesives, paints, or upholstery. However, most of the market for these products is still dominated by petrol-based alternatives, and according to the recent concerns about the economy circularisation, as well as the petrol rising price and reserves depletion, several studies have been conducted to find suitable renewable raw materials for the production of bio-based / green alternatives. (Paraskar, Prabhudesai, Hatkar, & Kulkarni, 2021; Karmakar, Ghosh, & Sharma, 2017) In addition to the higher biodegradability and reduced toxicity, these novel alternatives also hold several distinct properties. For example, biolubricants, compared to conventional fossil lubricants, demonstrate higher viscosity index, good lubricity, improved anti-corrosion properties, or higher flash point (Karmakar, Ghosh, & Sharma, 2017), whereas bio-based PUs present more toughness, more mechanical, corrosion and chemical resistance, or low-temperature flexibility (Paraskar, Prabhudesai, Hatkar, & Kulkarni, 2021).

It is in this sense that vegetable oils (VOs) have emerged as an alternative feedstock to petrol for the production of lubricants and polyols as precursors to PU production. VOs consists of triacylglycerides (TAGs) whose predominant radical esters are oleic (C 18:1 ω -9), linoleic (C 18:2 ω -6), and α -linolenic (C 18:3 ω -6) acids chains (Karmakar, Ghosh, & Sharma, 2017). However, these compounds have to undergo chemical modifications either via the carboxyl group or C=C bonds (unsaturations) of the carbon chain. Among the most widely used reactions in the synthesis of biopolyols are epoxidation, ozonolysis, hydroformylation, olefin metathesis, amidation-esterification or coupling of thiol-ene with mercaptoethanol (Paraskar, Prabhudesai, Hatkar, & Kulkarni, 2021; Sawpan, 2018). Regarding the biolubricants and its bio-base additives production, reactions such as transesterification, hydrolysis, amination, amidation, reduction to alcohol, epoxidation, carbonation of epoxy fatty esters or polymerisation are typically performed (Karmakar, Ghosh, & Sharma, 2017).

Nevertheless, according to Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) due to the environmental, food competition and LUC concerns inherent to the intensive planting of oil crops such as oil palm, soybean, sunflower, or rape (Jez, et al., 2017; FAO, 2022), the uncertainties arising from climate change or the war in Ukraine (FAO, 2022), as well as the more than 10 times higher price of VOs compared to crude oil (Destiarni & Jamil, 2021), the interest in analogous low-cost oils such as waste cooking oils (WCO) (Li & Wang, 2015; Asare, Souza, & Gupta, 2022) or microbial oils (MOs) produced from residual substrates (Sajish, Singh, & Nain, 2022) have strongly grown in a narrative of greater market competitiveness and minimal environmental impacts.

Figure 5. Proposal of a valorisation route of CS to biolubricants and bio-based PU materials. Adapted from Precision Urethane (2023), Lubgraf Synoils (2023) and Minchin (2021).

1.4. Oleaginous microorganisms: yeasts as prominent MOs factories

The designation of “oleaginous” is attributed to all living microorganisms, including bacteria, microalgae, filamentous fungi, or yeasts, capable of accumulating more than 20 % of their dry cell weight (DCW) in intracellular MOs, which composition profile may be comparable to some VOs. Compared to the latter, MOs

present multiple advantages such as the opportunity to valorise several low-cost residual feedstocks, the wide availability of microorganisms specialised for each feedstock, the high productivity and quality, the lower water and fertile land area requirements, or their immunity to climate change (Szczepańska, Hapeta, & Lazar, 2022). Conversely, according to a recent techno-economic study for a 48 kton MOs / year production facility, the price per kg of MO could achieve € 1.12 (Karamerou, Parsons, McManus, & Chuck, 2021), a discouraging value when compared, for instance, with the prices per kg of crude oil or VO's such as palm, soybean, sunflower or rapeseed oils of € 0.45, € 0.91, € 1.04, € 1.00 or € 0.98 on March 2023 (The World Bank, 2023).

In fact, although some MOs rich in rare fatty acids (FAs) are already commercialised today – e.g., eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) produced by the yeast *Yarrowia lipolytica* sp., docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) produced by the microalga *Cryptocodinium colinii* sp., or γ -linolenic acid (C 18:3 ω -6) produced from the filamentous fungi *Mucor circinelloides* sp. –, cost-effectiveness remains the limiting factor for industrialisation of most MOs production processes, being estimated that about 80 % of the overall costs arising from the price of the high-purity substrates, namely glucose. This fact has ultimately encouraged researchers around the world to develop analogous processes using residual feedstocks such as waste glycerol, sugar beet molasses, WCO, wastepaper, agrifood wastes, industrial wastewaters and sludges, among others (Sundaramahalingam, Sivashanmugam, Rajeshbanu, & Ashokkumar, 2022; Szczepańska, Hapeta, & Lazar, 2022; Sitepu, et al., 2014).

Besides the low-cost feedstocks use, other strategies could be adopted aiming at increasing the economic feasibility of these processes including the optimisation of the pre-treatment, hydrolysis, fermentation, cell harvesting, and MOs purification steps, the minimisation of energy costs associated with aeration, agitation and control, the adoption of non-sterile conditions, a continuous mode of operation, the use of zero-cost renewable energy, the valorisation of all the outflow waste streams (e.g., disrupted cells and wastewater), or the selection of an optimal performance thermotolerant microorganism (Karamerou, Parsons, McManus, & Chuck, 2021; Sitepu, et al., 2014).

In this sense, the optimum oleaginous microorganism for proposal of MOs production from CSH must meet some criteria such as high lipid productivities, yields and titres, a selective production of TAGs without the simultaneous synthesis of by-products, metabolic robustness to the presence of a wide range of substrates such as glucose, xylose, organic acids, aromatic compounds, etc., as well as a high tolerance to the presence of inhibitors (Broos, et al., 2022). Among the various oleaginous microorganisms, photoautotrophic microalgae have been highlighted for their simultaneous ability to produce high quantities of MOs and capture CO₂, emerging as an opportunity for the decarbonisation of industries strongly emitting GHG (Selvan, Chandrasekaran, Muthusamy, & Ramamurthy, 2023; Jez, et al., 2017). However, their intermittency associated with the sunlight necessity, the large land areas required for photobioreactors, their prone to contamination by bacteria and protozoa, or the higher operating costs, have moved attention to other microorganisms, with a focus on yeasts (Sundaramahalingam, Sivashanmugam, Rajeshbanu, & Ashokkumar, 2022; Sitepu, et al., 2014).

Compared to other oleaginous microorganisms, yeasts present several advantages, such as faster growth, easier scale-up, amenability to genetic mutations, versatility in consuming a wide range of carbon sources including glucose, xylose, glycerol, organic acids, polysaccharides and also alkanes, greater energy profitability and greater environmental sustainability of their processes (Sajish, Singh, & Nain, 2022; Chmielarz, 2021; Sundaramahalingam, Sivashanmugam, Rajeshbanu, & Ashokkumar, 2022). Currently, it is estimated that more than 70 of the 1600 known yeast species are oleaginous, which can still be distinguished mainly in the phyla Ascomycota – e.g., *Lipomyces starkeyi*, or *Y. lipolytica* – and Basidiomycota – e.g., *Rhodotorula glutinis*, or *Rhodotorula toruloides* (Chmielarz, 2021; Szczepańska, Hapeta, & Lazar, 2022). Phenotypically, the oleaginous yeasts belonging to the second phylum are essentially distinguished by their ability to grow in vitamin-poor media and by the formation of multiple small lipid bodies (LB), whereas the yeasts belonging to the first phylum generally require nutritionally rich media to grow and form a single large LB in the cytoplasm. Due to the cost associated with supplementation of culture media with vitamins, most of basidiomycetes yeasts have shown to be more economically promising (Sitepu, et al., 2014; Chmielarz, 2021). In particular, some oleaginous yeasts including strains belonging to the genera *Rhodotorula* or *Trichosporon* may even accumulate up to around 80 % of their DCW in MOs (Arora, Yen, & Philippidis, 2020).

1.4.1. Lipid synthesis in oleaginous yeasts

The biosynthesis of TAGs in oleaginous yeast occurs essentially via *de novo* pathway, i.e., from excess carbohydrates such as glucose or xylose under nutritional stress (e.g., nitrogen deficiency), and via *ex novo* pathway, i.e., from lipophilic substrates including free FAs present in the culture medium, the former being promoted under the conditions found in lignocellulosic hydrolysates. Briefly, during the *de novo* pathway carbon sources like glucose, xylose or glycerol enter the cell and are converted to pyruvate by the conventional pathways. Pyruvate, in turn, is conducted into the mitochondria by the monocarboxylic acid transporter (MCT) and converted to acetyl-CoA by pyruvate dehydrogenase (PDH), and then incorporated into the Krebs Cycle. Under nitrogen-limiting conditions, AMP deaminase breaks AMP into inosine monophosphate (IMO) as a way of obtaining ammonium ions, which in turn will cease the activity of isocitrate dehydrogenase (IDH) whose activation depends on AMP. Once the Krebs cycle is interrupted at this point, the citrate ion will accumulate and, from a given critical point, it will be expelled into the cytoplasm by the citrate-malate translocase (CMT) exchanging with the malate ion present in the cytoplasm. The citrate now present in the cytoplasm is converted to acetyl-CoA by ATP-citrate lyase (ACL), which proceeds to the TAGs synthesis pathways in the endoplasmic reticulum (ER). In parallel, oxaloacetate is again converted to malate by malate dehydrogenase (MDH), in order to maintain the efflux of citrate ions through CMT. On the other hand, acetate, also present in lignocellulosic hydrolysates in equilibrium with the inhibitory form of acetic acid once in the cytoplasm can be directly metabolized to acetyl-CoA and forwarded to the TAGs synthesis pathways in the ER. (Chmielarz, 2021; Szczepańska, Hapeta, & Lazar, 2022; Sundaramahalingam, Sivashanmugam, Rajeshbanu, & Ashokkumar, 2022)

Figure 6. Simplified scheme of TAGs synthesis and accumulation into LB in oleaginous yeasts under nitrogen limiting conditions (*de novo* pathway). Adapted from Chmielarz (2021).

Still, the metabolism of TAGs may be affected by different factors, which might lead to variations in the performance and quality of the produced MOs, including the nutrient ratio C:N, C:P, C:S, etc., the type of nutrients source and their effective concentration in the hydrolysate, operating conditions such as oxygen supply, pH, or temperature, or even the presence of inhibitory compounds (Sitepu, et al., 2014).

1.4.2. Optimal CSH-performing oleaginous yeasts?

As discussed before, the choice of the best performing yeast in CSH represents one of the most relevant steps from the point of view of the design of a MOs production process. Even in the last years, several strains of oleaginous yeasts have been described for successfully growing on lignocellulosic hydrolysates, some of them belonging to the species *Rhodotorula babjevae*, *R. toruloides* or *Trichosporon oleaginosus* (Shaigani, et al., 2021; Brandenburg, et al., 2021).

R. toruloides is a heterothallic dimorphism yeast belonging to the *Sporidiobolaceae* family, *Sporidiobolales* order, *Microbotryomycetes* class and *Basidiomycota* phylum, which, in nature, may be found in pine wood pulp, soil, seawater, acid sewage or plant leaves, either in yeast or in mycelial forms (Wen, Zhang, Odoh, & Zhao, 2020). Phenotypically, its cells can present either a spherical or elongated morphology and may accumulate high lipids and carotenoids contents, these latter organic pigments responsible for a pink/orange/red hue, depending on their composition (Coradetti, et al., 2018). Carotenoids synthesised by *Rhodotorula* yeasts mainly includes torulene (3',4'-didehydro- β , ψ -carotene), torularhodin (3',4'-didehydro- β , ψ -caroten-16-oic acid), and minor quantities of β -carotene (Dufossé, 2009). Besides their use as natural edible colouring agents,

these carotenoids also present antioxidant and anticancer bioactivities, making them molecules of high interest to the chemical, pharmaceutical, feed, and cosmetics industries (Qi, et al., 2022). In particular, under nutritional limitations of nitrogen, sulphur, phosphorus, sulphate or iron the accumulation of lipids is enhanced, with a maximum total lipid content recorded of 76 % of its DCW for this species (Chattopadhyay & Maiti, 2021). Generally, this specie has been characterized as efficiently consuming carbon and energy sources including glucose, xylose, sucrose, maltose, cellobiose trehalose, raffinose, melezitose, ethanol, glycerol, mannitol, sorbitol, acetate, lactate, succinate, citrate, long-chain FAs or D-galacturonic acid, and nitrogen sources including ammonium ions, nitrate ions, cadaverine, amino acids or small peptides, (Wen, Zhang, Odoh, & Zhao, 2020; Coradetti, et al., 2018) making it suitable for grow in different waste streams such as lignocellulosic hydrolysates, crude glycerol or molasses (Albertyn & Viljoen, 2014). This specie is also known for its high tolerance to several inhibitory compounds and osmotic stress (Wen, Zhang, Odoh, & Zhao, 2020; Hu, Zhao, Zhao, Wu, & Zhao, 2009; Coradetti, et al., 2018).

R. babjevae is a mucoid non-ballistosporogenous teliospore-forming yeast that, due to its taxonomic proximity to *R. toruloides*, presents several similarities with the latter, namely its ability to produce carotenoids of high commercial interest (Seveiri, et al., 2020; Martín-Hernández, et al., 2022). However, it may be distinguished by an oval cell morphology and by the excretion of polyol esters of fatty acids (PEFA), a family of glycolipids with surfactant properties, into the extracellular medium under conditions of nutritional deficiencies and excess carbon. Besides promoting the reduction of the superficial tension of the culture media, these PEFA – mainly sophorolipids – also present high biodegradability, low toxicity and antifungal, antibacterial, antiviral, and anti-carcinogenic bioactivities, which confer to this specie a higher relevance in the pharmaceutical and environmental industries (Guerfali, et al., 2019; Sandberg, 2019; Pedras, et al., 2022; Sen, Borah, Bora, & Deka, 2017).

T. oleaginosus, also designated as *Candida curvata*, *Apiotrichum curvatum*, *Cryptococcus curvatus*, *Trichosporon cutaneum*, or *Cutaneotrichosporon oleaginosus*, is an oval or spherical arthroconidia-forming yeast belonging to the *Tremellaceae* family, *Tremellales* order, *Tremellomycetes* class and *Basidiomycota* phylum, widely found in nature, for instance in soil or plant leaves residues (Chattopadhyay & Maiti, 2021; Fidio, Minonne, Antonetti, & Galletti, 2021). This specie is also able to utilise a broad range of carbon and energy sources such as glucose, xylose, galactose, arabinose, galacturonic acid, N-acetylglycosamine, cellobiose, sucrose, lactose, glycerol, acetate, propionate, butyrate, or ethanol, (Meo, Priebe, & Weuster-Botz, 2017; Bracharz, Beukhout, Mehlmer, & Brück, 2017; Patel, Sarkar, Rova, Christakopoulos, & Matsakas, 2021) or nitrogen sources such as ammonium ions, nitrate ions and urea, as well as tolerate the presence of inhibitory compounds similarly to the above-mentioned species, which allows it to grow on complex residual media including lignocellulosic hydrolysates, organic acids, agrifood waste or sewage sludges (Bracharz, Beukhout, Mehlmer, & Brück, 2017; Fidio, Minonne, Antonetti, & Galletti, 2021). Remarkably, a maximum lipid content of 82.7 % of DCW has already been recorded for this specie (Chattopadhyay & Maiti, 2021).

Figure 7. Relevant phenotypic aspects to the species *R. toruloides* (a and d), *R. babjevae* (b and e) and *T. oleaginosus* (c and f). Legend: a/b/c – Appearance of colonies on YM agar plates, retrieved from Microbe Division (JCM) (2023); d/e/f – Cell morphology under the optical microscope at a magnification of 1000× during stationary phase (this work).

The FAs profile is also a phenotypic characteristic that is distinctive between species, although it may also vary according to the growing conditions and stage of development of the culture (i Nogué, et al., 2018). Thus, **Table 1** shows some example FAs profiles for the yeast species *R. toruloides*, *R. babjevae* and *T. oleaginosus*.

Table 1. Examples of FAs profiles for the three oleaginous species *R. toruloides*, *R. babjevae* and *T. oleaginosus*.

Specie	C 16:0	C 16:1	C 18:0	C 18:1	C 16:2	C 16:3	Reference
	% w/w	% w/w	% w/w	% w/w	% w/w	% w/w	
<i>R. toruloides</i>	18 - 37	1	3 - 36	19 - 60	2 - 13	0 - 3.5	(Szczepańska, Hapeta, & Lazar, 2022)
<i>R. babjevae</i>	22.4	2.6	1.6	54.5	11.5	4.1	(Brandenburg, 2021)
<i>T. oleaginosus</i>	26 - 32	-	6 - 15	44 - 67	5 - 10	-	(Szczepańska, Hapeta, & Lazar, 2022)

In the **Table 2**, some relevant results in the context of MOs production from lignocellulosic hydrolysates, with special emphasis on CSH, by different strains of yeast *R. babjevae*, *R. toruloides* and *T. oleaginosus* are briefly reviewed.

Table 2. Brief review of some relevant results for the three oleaginous species *R. toruloides*, *R. babjevae* and *T. oleaginosus*, when grown on lignocellulosic hydrolysates with emphasis on CSH, in terms of final biomass and accumulated lipid content.

Specie	Strain	System	Medium	Final biomass (g _{DCW} /L)	Lipids content (% w/w of DCW)	Reference
<i>R. toruloides</i>	NRRL Y-1091	Flask (batch)	CSH	43	61	(Slininger, et al., 2016)
	DSMZ 4444	Bioreactor (batch)	CSH	38	61 (FAs)	(i Nogué, et al., 2018)
	DSMZ 4444	Flask (fed-batch)	CSH	54	59	(Fei, et al., 2016)
<i>R. babjevae</i>	CBS 14	Flask (batch)	Wheat straw hydrolysate (WSH)	30	39	(Brandenburg, et al., 2021)
	DBVPG 8058	Flask (batch)	WSH	28	65	(Brandenburg, et al., 2021)
<i>T. oleaginosus</i>	ATCC 20509	Flask (batch)	CSH	11	61	(Gong, et al., 2016)
	ATCC 20509	Bioreactor (batch)	CSH	34	63 (FAs)	(i Nogué, et al., 2018)
	AS 2.571	Bioreactor (batch)	CSH	19	39	(Hu, et al., 2011)
	DSM 11815	Flask (batch)	WSH + Corn Steep Liquor (CSL)	15	51	(Shaigani P., et al., 2021)

1.5. FC as a tool for bioprocess optimisation

FC is an instrumental technique that allows the rapid detection and biological and/or physical characterization of individual cells and solid particles suspended in a saline buffer solution based on their fluorescence or light scattering properties (McKinnon, 2018; Edwards, Oprea, Prossnitz, & Sklar, 2004). Properties such as size, granularity, oxidative stress, membrane integrity, membrane potential, lipid accumulation, or enzymatic activity, are some of the most relevant examples of the information that can be acquired from this technique (Silva, Roseiro, & Reis, 2012). Among the main advantages of this technique compared to classic microbiological techniques are the high-throughput, high reliability, or the collection of information from each individual of a population without the generalisation with an average value (Chantzoura & Kaji, 2017; Adan, Alizada, Kiraz, Baran, & Nalbant, 2017).

The main system components of a conventional flow cytometer are the microfluidics, optics, and electronic detectors (**Figure 8**) (Adan, Alizada, Kiraz, Baran, & Nalbant, 2017; McKinnon, 2018).

Figure 8. Simplified scheme of the main components of a conventional flow cytometer. Legend: FSC – forward scatter; SSC – side scatter; PMT – photomultiplier tubes; PD – photodiodes. Adapted from Adan, Alizada, Kiraz, Baran, & Nalbant, (2017).

The microfluidics system includes two components, the sheath fluid – e.g., phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) or ultra-pure water –, and the pressurised air. During the analysis, the cell and/or solid suspension present in the sample is drawn and injected into the central core of the flow chamber at a constant flow rate by the action of pressurised air. The pressure of the sheath fluid stream is regulated in order to ensure a laminar flow throughout the chamber. In this way, the phenomenon known as hydrodynamic focusing is promoted, in which cells and solid particles from the sample are aligned in a single file passing one by one through one or more laser beams, where light scattering or fluorochromes excitation occur (Yang & Hsieh, 2007; Adan, Alizada, Kiraz, Baran, & Nalbant, 2017; Silva, Roseiro, & Reis, 2012). The sample and sheath fluid streams circulate at very high flow rates, which allows processing up to 10^4 events/s (Brehm-Stecher, 2014).

In general, the optical system consists of one or more radiation sources, i.e., lasers or mercury lamps, lenses for shaping and focusing laser beams, and optical bandpass filters and mirrors units for selection of a specific wavelength and for redirection of light beams, respectively. The electrical system, on the other hand, has as its main components the optical detectors that can comprise two types, photomultiplier tubes (PMT) or photodiodes (PD), which convert the fluorescence or light scattering signals into electronic currents that are then amplified and visualised in cytograms (Adan, Alizada, Kiraz, Baran, & Nalbant, 2017; McKinnon, 2018). One of the most relevant optical properties in FC is the light scattering, which fundamentally depends on the shape and topography of the cell, on its granularity, and on cellular materials such as membranes or the nucleus. Forward scattering (FSC) is detected collinearly to the laser beam by a PD detector and its signal is proportional to the surface area or size of the cell, while side scattering (SSC) is detected perpendicularly to

the laser beam by a PMT detector and the corresponding signal is proportional to the granularity or internal complexity of the cell (Adan, Alizada, Kiraz, Baran, & Nalbant, 2017; Silva, Roseiro, & Reis, 2012; McKinnon, 2018). It is common to intercept both signals plotting FSC versus SSC (**Figure 9**), which allows differentiating different cells populations in a heterogeneous population (Adan, Alizada, Kiraz, Baran, & Nalbant, 2017).

Figure 9. Schematic illustration of the interpretation of a cytogram in terms of FSC versus SSC signals. Left image adapted from Adan, Alizada, Kiraz, Baran, & Nalbant (2017).

In order to access additional information about a given suspension of cells and/or solids, sometimes it is advantageous to make use of fluorescence, either by transfection and expression of fluorescent proteins, by staining with fluorescent dyes (fluorochromes) or by immunostaining with fluorescently conjugated antibodies (McKinnon, 2018). In particular, fluorochromes may selectively bind to cellular components or macromolecules – e.g., nucleic acids, proteins, or lipids – or suffer biochemical transformations inside the cells, for instance, by the action of pH, membrane polarization, or enzymatic activity (Silva, Roseiro, & Reis, 2012). Briefly, when struck by a laser beam, fluorochromes absorb light in a given range of wavelengths, becoming in the excited state, and then, when returning to the ground state, the molecule emits radiation in a higher specific range of wavelengths, being thus detected by the corresponding PMT (**Figure 11**). In order to identify a positive fluorescence signal, a prior control performed without staining is required as a negative background (Adan, Alizada, Kiraz, Baran, & Nalbant, 2017).

Propidium iodide (PI) is a fluorochrome widely used in FC for membrane integrity detection since it is only able to enter the cells when permeabilised or injured cytoplasmic. Once inside the cells, this compound binds to nucleic acids, namely DNA and RNA, by intercalation between nucleotides, emitting fluorescence. PI has an excitation peak at 535 nm (green region), and an emission peak at 615 nm (orange region) (**Figure 10**) (Rosenberg, Azevedo, & Ivask, 2019; Beckman Coulter, 2023). It is common to use this fluorochrome for membrane-damaged cell counting purposes, for which it is necessary to double-staining PI with another compound able to diffuse through intact membranes and also bind to nucleic acids, such as SYBR Green I (SGI), allowing also the total cell counting (Nescerecka, Hammes, & Juhna, 2016). SGI, on the other hand, shows an excitation peak at 498 nm (turquoise blue region), with a corresponding emission peak at 522 nm (green region) (**Figure 10**) (AAT Bioquest, 2023).

Figure 10. Excitation and emission spectra for SGI and PI in terms of relative intensity versus wavelength. Adapted from Beckman Coulter (2023).

By using a double-staining method, it is possible to distinguish, on one hand, cells from solid particles, since SGI and PI only bind to DNA and RNA, and on the other hand, cells with intact membranes from cells with permeabilised or injured membranes, in face of total cells (**Figure 11**). However, due to the fact that the emission spectrum of SGI coincides with the excitation spectrum of PI, it may induce an energy transfer between the two compounds in such a way that quenching of the green fluorescence of SGI occurs with consequent increase in the fluorescence of PI, something already observed before for double-staining with SYTO 9 and PI (Nescerecka, Hammes, & Juhna, 2016).

Figure 11. Mechanism of fluorescence (left) and schematic illustration of the interpretation of a cytogram in terms of SGI versus PI fluorescence signals. Left image adapted from Adan, Alizada, Kiraz, Baran, & Nalbant (2017).

In general, FC is a powerful biotechnological tool that allows obtaining, near real-time, robust information on cell physiological status, during microbial cultures evolution. In the present study, this technique was used to monitor oleaginous yeast cultures grown on lignocellulosic hydrolysates, which are known to contain inhibitor compounds that may affect the cell metabolism. Such approach allows understanding the cell stress-response to environment, also allowing a fast and precise optimisation and scale-up of the present bioprocess for CSH valorisation (Silva, Roseiro, & Reis, 2012).

2. Proposal

The study presented in this thesis proposed the selection of one optimal-performing oleaginous yeast strain, among three candidates, a *Rhodotorula babjevae* sp., a *Trichosporon oleaginosus* sp. and a *Rhodotorula toruloides* sp., at a scale of 150 mL in 1-L Erlenmeyer flasks, aiming at valorising the CSH, obtained by enzymatic hydrolysis preceded by STEX, to produce intracellular MOs suitable for the production of biolubricants and bio-based PUs. Afterwards, the selected strain was cultivated at a scale of 2 L in a 7 L-bioreactor, expecting to further optimise and scale-up this bioprocess in a pilot facility with a total capacity of 100 m³. In parallel, a double-staining method, using fluorescent stains SGI and PI, coupled with FC analysis, was optimised, and further used to monitor the yeast cultivations conducted in a 7L-bioreactor, for cell membrane integrity detection.

For all the trials, the cultures were monitored over the incubation time through the DCW, optical density at 600 nm ($OD_{600\text{ nm}}$), pH readings, and the glucose, xylose, acetic acid, formic acid, HMF and furfural residual concentrations in the culture broth, and at the final instant, the total lipids, and total FAs, as well as FAs profile, were also determined. For each experiment, the growth, substrates uptake and lipid accumulation kinetic parameters were calculated. Particularly in the bioreactor cultivation, the culture was also monitored for Kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN) content and by FC analysis, in order to obtain, near real-time, physiological information about the cells such as the relative size, internal complexity, and membrane integrity, and total cells counting.

This work arises within the scope of FRONTSH1P European project, A FRONTrunner approach to Systemic circular, Holistic & Inclusive solutions for a New Paradigm of territorial circular economy.

3. Materials and methods

3.1. Yeast strains, maintenance, and reactivation

A preliminary screening test was carried out to select the best yeast strain in terms of lipid production. Three oleaginous yeast strains were tested: *R. babjevae* sp., *T. oleaginosus* sp., and a *R. toruloides* sp.. The microorganisms were stored at 4 °C, on malt extract agar (MEA) slants.

The reactivation of the cells was carried out by transferring cells from the slants to fresh MEA slants and further incubation at 30 °C (or 25 °C for *R. babjevae*) (oven SANYO, MIR-253, JP), for 72 h.

3.2. Residual feedstock

3.2.1. CSH

CS, kindly supplied by Company A, was used as feedstock. In order to release fermentable monosaccharides from corn stover, this was subject to a pre-treatment stage prior to enzymatic hydrolysis. Pre-treatment was based on a non-catalysed steam explosion technology, i.e., without the addition of acids and using only high-pressure steam. After pre-treatment, the solid fraction was washed with water and further submitted to an enzymatic hydrolysis stage. CSH was obtained after enzymatic saccharification of the pre-treated solid by applying Cellic® CTec3 (Novozymes, DK). The resulting hydrolysate was centrifuged at 12000×g, for 15 min, at 4 °C (SIGMA, 6-16KS, DE), to remove the unreacted solids and then appropriately stored (frozen) until use.

The hydrolysate was analysed by high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) (3.8.2), exhibiting the following composition: 45.0 ± 0.6 g/L of glucose, 21.8 ± 0.4 g/L of xylose, 0.95 ± 0.01 g/L of formic acid, 2.97 ± 0.04 g/L of acetic acid, 136 ± 3 mg/L of furfural and 64 ± 1 mg/L of HMF (vestigial). This was further analysed by the Kjeldahl method (3.9), resulting in a trace TKN value of 0.246 ± 0.002 mg N/g.

3.2.2. CSL

CSL was gently provided by Company B, as a by-product of this starch industry during the corn wet-milling step. The liquor was analysed by HPLC (3.8.2) and the Kjeldahl method (3.9), presenting a lactic acid concentration of 0.114 ± 0.001 g/g and a TKN value of 28.2 ± 0.4 mg N/g, correspondingly.

3.3. Reagents and culture media components

The reagents and culture media components used in this work are listed in **Appendix I**.

3.4. Inocula preparation

For each microorganism, inocula were prepared in duplicate by transferring cells from two slants to 150 mL of a sterile liquid medium containing 20 g/L of Dextrose, 20 g/L of Peptone and 10 g/L of Yeast Extract (YPD), at pH 5.5, in baffled 1 L-Erlenmeyer flasks. Incubation was carried out at the studied temperatures – 25 or 30 °C, depending on the strain – under orbital shaking at 120 rpm for 24 h (INFORS HT Unitron, USA). At that time the cells entered the exponential phase. The inocula cultures were observed under an optical microscope (3.11) to detect possible contaminations.

3.5. Batch cultures for yeast screening

3.5.1. Screening in CSH-mimic synthetic medium

The three promising oleaginous yeasts were inoculated (10 % v/v) in 135 mL of a sterile synthetic liquid medium, to simulate the composition of a CSH previously studied (**Table 3**), supplemented with 6.7 g/L Yeast Nitrogen Base (YNB) and 5 g/L of glucose monohydrate, at pH 5.5, in baffled 1L-Erlenmeyers.

Table 3. Average composition for a CSH, previously obtained at laboratory scale, and characterized by HPLC.

Glucose	Xylose	Acetic acid	Formic acid	HMF	Furfural
(g/L)	(g/L)	(g/L)	(g/L)	(g/L)	(g/L)
54.3 ± 2.0	18.7 ± 0.8	3.0 ± 0.0	0.8 ± 0.0	0.04 ± 0.0	0.21 ± 0.0

The cultures were incubated at the studied temperatures – 25 or 30 °C, depending on the strain – at 120 rpm (INFORS HT Unitron, USA) until stationary phase was reached. For each microorganism, a control experiment consisting of the sterile medium without cells was conducted in parallel with the yeast cultures.

In order to determine the biomass concentration, substrates consumption (glucose and xylose) and inhibitory compounds concentration (acetic and formic acids, HMF and furfural), small volumes of culture broth were collected throughout the cultivation time. For each sample taken, the pH value was measured by potentiometry (Consort, C3021, BE), the biomass concentration was quantified by gravimetry and turbidimetry (3.8.1), and the residual above-referred compounds concentrations was quantified by HPLC (3.8.2). At the end of cultivations, culture broths were centrifuged at 8000 rpm, for 8 min, at 4 °C (SIGMA, 6-16KS, DE) to collect the wet cellular pellet, which was stored in the freezer (-18 °C) for subsequent freeze-drying at -55 °C, for 24 h (Heto PowerDry LL3000 Freeze Dryer system from Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA, coupled to a Vacubrand RZ 2.5 vacuum pump, DE). The final freeze-dried biomass was then stored in the freezer for further FAs characterization and quantification, by gas-liquid chromatography equipped with a flame ionization detector (FID-GC) (3.8.3), and total lipids quantification, by the Soxhlet method (3.8.4).

Figure 12. Systematized experimental procedure for the screening of the three oleaginous yeasts in semi-defined CSH-mimic synthetic medium.

3.5.2. Screening in CSH + CSL complex medium

After testing the three strains in the CSH-mimic synthetic medium, these three yeast strains were further cultivated in 150 mL of a sterile complex medium, composed of CSH as carbon source, CSL as nitrogen source, a mineral medium and deionized water (unpublished composition), previously adjusted to pH 5.5, in baffled 1L-Erlenmeyer flasks. Contrarily to the protocol described in 3.5.1 section, in this procedure two inocula were selected and diluted, whenever necessary, to an $OD_{600\text{ nm}}$ of 12.15, following their total volume to centrifugation at 8000 rpm, for 8 min, at 4 °C (SIGMA, 6-16KS, DE). For each inoculum, the resulting cell pellet was resuspended in 40 mL of culture medium, from which 15 mL were distributed to each of the two replicates. However, since the medium culture, without cells, contained many particles, it was necessary to discount them to the medium culture with cells, to eliminate the particles interference with the yeast biomass quantification. In this sense, 1 mL of the non-inoculated medium and medium culture with cells were centrifuged at 8000 rpm, for 8 min (Heraeus Sepatech Biofuge 15, DE), and the supernatants were discarded. The tubes containing the pellets were freeze-dried together with the final biomasses and then oven-dried at 100 °C for further weighing.

Figure 13. Systematized experimental procedure for the screening of the three yeasts in complex hydrolysate.

The *Total Solids (TS) % w/w* content (in a dry basis) was, thus, determined as follows.

$$TS \% w/w = \frac{w \text{ dry solids}}{w \text{ dry biomass}} \times 10$$

3.6. Lab-scale bioreactor experiment

Attempting to scale-up the process, once the best performing strain was selected, a benchtop stirred-tank reactor (STR) with 7 L total volume (Electrolab Biotech, Fermac 310, UK) system was operated in fed-batch/batch modes. The bioreactor body consists of a borosilicate culture vessel with a cylindrical geometry, comprising an air sparger, a 6-blade Rushton impeller, an electric heating jacket, a water-cooled coil, a thermocouple slot, a pH electrode, a pO₂ polarographic electrode and four metallic baffles, whose main dimensions are shown below.

Figure 14. Overall dimensions and schematic representation of the bioreactor body, baffles, turbine, sparger, heating jacket and cooling coil. Note that the figure is not to scale.

The pH electrode (METTLER TOLEDO, InPro® 3030/325, CH) is calibrated prior to the sterilisation step, by setting the pH values at 4.01 and 7.00 accordingly to commercial buffer solutions (HACH™, USA). The oxygen electrode (METTLER TOLEDO, CH) must be calibrated after sterilisation and polarisation for, at least, 6 h. Hence, after the sterilisation step, the relative dissolved oxygen tension (DO), in %, was set at 0 %, by inflowing a N₂ stream (Air Liquide, ALPHAGAZ™ 1 N₂, FR) in the medium, throughout a 0.22 µm sterile filter, at 1 vvm, and at 100 %, by inflowing an air stream, at 1 vvm, 30 °C and 200 rpm.

One cultivation with a liquid volume of 2 L was carried out, using a semi-defined CSH-mimic synthetic medium, with a carbon pulse addition, respecting the same formulation mentioned above, in section 3.5.2. In this sense, a small volume (50 mL) of a concentrated pulse of glucose 409 g/L and xylose 204 g/L was added after 51.7 h

of cultivation, assuming negligible any variation in liquid volume. Additionally, polypropylene glycol (PPG) 425 anti-foaming agent was added whenever the foam formation was excessive.

The most relevant aspects concerning the bioreactor cultivation are, therefore, reviewed in **Table 4**.

Table 4. Key aspects considered in the bioreactor cultivation.

Cultivation period	Operation mode	Liquid volume (L)	Initial media composition (v/v)	Carbon pulse specifications	Anti-foaming agent	Stirring speed (rpm)
68.2 h	Fed-batch (carbon pulse addition)	2	CSH-mimic synthetic medium + CSL + mineral medium + water	Glucose 409 g/L Xylose 204 g/L (50 mL, 51.7 h)	PPG 425 (non-diluted)	100 - 220

The diagram corresponding to the experimental set-up is shown in **Figure 15**.

Figure 15. Schematic diagram of the experimental set-up, including fluid and air piping, cooling-water utility line, control linkages and accessories (pumps, rotor, exhaust air condenser, valves, sterilisation filters, and rotameter). Legend: PID – proportional-integral-differential controllers.

Temperature and pH parameters were kept constant at set-points of 30 °C and 5.5, respectively, through dedicated PID feedback controllers. The temperature was kept constant by a thermostat system composed of a jacket heating involving the vessel, and an external cooling water flow, while the pH was kept constant at 5.5, by the addition of HCl 2.5 M and NaOH 2.5 M solutions. The stirring speed parameter was set manually, regarding the needs of the culture over the cultivation time and the foam formation. The aeration flow rate was

maintained at 1 vvm all over the time. Real-time registration of stirring speed and DO, in %, was done using the Electrolab Fermentation Manager software (Electrolab Biotech, UK). All the system and solutions were pre-sterilised, and all air inlets of the system were fitted with sterilising polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) filters with a 0.2 μm porosity (Sartorius, Midisart[®] 2000, DE). Tap water was used as the cooling agent. All collected samples were submitted to analogous processing, described in 3.5.1. Once a day, samples were run in FC (3.10) for cell size, intracellular complexity, and membrane integrity detection, as well as total cells counting.

3.7. Microbial kinetics parameters

3.7.1. Growth

For a given batch microbial culture, the mass balance is expressed by the following equation (unstructured Malthus model):

$$\frac{dX_v}{dt} = r_x = (\mu - k_d) \cdot X_v \quad (2)$$

Where r_x denotes the volumetric rate of cell biomass accumulation, X_v the concentration of viable cells in reproductive state, μ the specific growth rate for the organism under study and k_d the specific cell death constant.

By integrating numerically between t_0 (inoculation time) and any time instant t , the previous expression is reconfigured as follows:

$$\int_{X_{v0}}^{X_v} \frac{1}{X_v} \cdot dX_v = \int_{t_0}^t (\mu - k_d) \cdot dt \Leftrightarrow \ln(X_v) = (\mu - k_d) \cdot (t - t_0) + \ln(X_{v0}) \quad (3)$$

In the absence of inhibition mechanisms, the specific growth rate correlates with the concentration of a given limiting substrate, S^L , by applying the Monod equation (1950):

$$\mu = \mu_{m\acute{a}x} \cdot \frac{S^L}{K_S + S^L} \quad (4)$$

In which $\mu_{m\acute{a}x}$ expresses the maximum biologically viable growth rate at constant temperature and pH conditions, and K_S the saturation constant, i.e., the S^L at which $\mu = \frac{1}{2}\mu_{m\acute{a}x}$.

In particular during the exponential growth phase, where $K_S \ll S^L$, it is inferred that the specific growth rate is maximum and constant ($\mu = \mu_{m\acute{a}x}$), as well as negligible the cell death term ($k_d \sim 0$), and supposing also that under these conditions $X_v \propto X_{DCW}$, the equation (3) can be simplified for any instant t comprised in this phase, so that it is possible to obtain the $\mu_{m\acute{a}x}$ by a linear regression:

$$\ln(X_{DCW}(t)) = \mu_{m\acute{a}x} \cdot t + \ln(X_{DCW,0}) \quad (5)$$

Note that X_{DCW} stand for DCW, obtained experimentally as explained in 3.8.1.

Besides the μ_{max} parameter, also the global and maximum volumetric productivities, $Prod_{vol.}(X)_{global}$ and $Prod_{vol.}(X)_{max.}$, can be calculated for each cultivation.

$$Prod_{vol.}(X)_{global} = \frac{X_{DCW}(t_{final}) - X_{DCW}(t_0)}{t_{final} - t_0} \quad (6)$$

$$Prod_{vol.}(X)_{max.} = \max_i \left\{ \frac{X_{DCW}(t_i) - X_{DCW}(t_0)}{t_i - t_0} \right\} \quad (7)$$

Once the substrate consumption profiles are known, it is additionally possible to estimate the global biomass/substrate yield coefficient, $Y_{X/S}$, for each cultivation, in terms of glucose and xylose.

$$Y_{X/S} = \frac{X_{DCW}(t_{final}) - X_{DCW}(t_0)}{S(t_0) - S(t_{final})} \quad (8)$$

Besides, considering the substrates uptake profiles it is also possible to calculate the respective global and maximum volumetric consumption rates, $-r_{S,global}$ and $-r_{S,max.}$, in terms of each above-mentioned detected molecule, as follows.

$$-r_{S,global} = \frac{S(t_0) - S(t_{final})}{t_{final} - t_0} \quad (9)$$

$$-r_{S,max.} = \max_i \left\{ \frac{S(t_{i-1}) - S(t_i)}{t_i - t_{i-1}} \right\} \quad (10)$$

3.7.2. Lipid production

It was established that the screening for the optimal performing yeast would be based on the parameters concerning the production of intracellular lipids (focusing on total FAs), namely, the global volumetric productivity of lipids and FAs, $Prod_{vol.}(L)_{global}$ and $Prod_{vol.}(FAs)_{global}$, respectively, and the global lipids/substrate, FAs/substrate, lipids/biomass and FAs/biomass yield coefficients, $Y_{L/S}$, $Y_{FAs/S}$, $Y_{L/X}$, and $Y_{FAs/X}$, calculated as shown below.

$$Prod_{vol.}(L)_{global} = \frac{[Total Lipids](t_{final})}{t_{final} - t_0} \quad (11)$$

$$Prod_{vol.}(FAs)_{global} = \frac{[Total FAs](t_{final})}{t_{final} - t_0} \quad (12)$$

$$Y_{L/S} = \frac{[Total Lipids](t_{final})}{S(t_0) - S(t_{final})} \quad (13)$$

$$Y_{FAs/S} = \frac{[Total FAs](t_{final})}{S(t_0) - S(t_{final})} \quad (14)$$

$$Y_{L/X} = \frac{[Total Lipids](t_{final})}{X_{DCW}(t_{final}) - X_{DCW}(t_0)}$$

$$Y_{FAs/X} = \frac{[Total\ FAs](t_{final})}{X_{DCW}(t_{final}) - X_{DCW}(t_0)} \quad (16)$$

3.8. Analytical procedures

3.8.1. Cellular quantification

The turbidimetric quantification of yeast biomass, for each culture broth sample, was performed by measuring the absorbance at a wavelength of 600 nm (Thermo Scientific™ GENESYS™ 20, USA) ($OD_{600\ nm}$) considered the region of maximum absorption of the yeast cells, assuming valid the Lambert-Beer law for a range of absorbances measured between 0.25 and 0.65, carrying out the necessary dilutions with deionized water. For samples taken from cultures in complex hydrolysate, the value of $OD_{600\ nm}$ of the respective non-inoculated medium was subtracted.

Alongside, the biomass concentration gravimetric quantification was performed by weighting the cell pellet correspondent to a precise 1 mL volume of culture broth, in dry basis, which will henceforth be referred to as dry cell weight (X_{DCW}). This strictly known volume of culture broth was initially centrifuged at 9000 rpm for 5 min (Heraeus Sepatech Biofuge 15, DE), being the remaining pellet washed and resuspended in 1 mL of deionized water. After a second centrifugation under the same conditions, the final pellet was oven-dried at 100 °C, overnight. In order to discount the fraction of solids inherent to the culture medium containing CSH and CSL, the respective non-inoculated medium was subjected to the same protocol.

Additionally, the total cells counting was carried out by FC, as described in 3.10.

3.8.2. Sugars, short-chain organic acids, and sugar-derived aldehydes quantification

The quantification of sugars (glucose and xylose), short-chain organic acids (acetic and formic) and sugar-derived aldehydes (HMF and furfural) in the frozen supernatants from the first centrifugation described in 3.5.1 was based on HPLC analysis. The most concentrated samples were diluted in ultra-pure water as necessary so that the corresponding concentrations could be interpolated from the calibration curves previously obtained from standards. Before transferring to appropriate vials, the samples were subjected to filtration through PTFE filters with a porosity of 0.22 μm and a diameter of 25 mm, from Labfil, retaining the solid particles, harmful to the chromatographic system.

For the required analysis, samples were automatically injected (5.0 μL) into an HPLC system (1260 Infinity II, Agilent, USA) equipped with a cation exchange column (Aminex HPX-87H, Bio-Rad, USA), a pre-column of equivalent charge (Bio-Rad, USA), a diode-array detector (DAD), for HMF and furfural quantification at 280 nm, and a refractive index detector (RID), for the quantification of the remaining analytes, the latter operating at 45 °C. Isocratic elution (H_2SO_4 , 5 mM) was performed at a flow rate of 0.6 mL/min at a column temperature of 50

°C. The analysis period was 60 min for all samples containing furans. All chromatograms were processed and integrated in the software OpenLab CDS 2.6 (Agilent, USA).

3.8.3. FAs characterization and quantification

The characterization and quantification of FAs present in the previously freeze-dried yeast biomass was performed by FID-GC, based on the corresponding methyl esters (FAMES), via transesterification procedure adapted from Lepage and Roy (1984). For each analyse, about 100 mg (of known moisture content, as further explained in 3.8.3.1) of freeze-dried sample were transferred into Schott test tubes, under N₂ inert atmosphere (Air Liquide, ALPHAGAZ™ 1 N₂, FR), followed by the addition of 2 mL of a methanol/acetyl chloride solution (95:5 % v/v) and 0.2 mL of a tridecanoic acid C13:0 solution (Nu-Chek-Prep, USA) (5 g/L in petroleum ether, boiling point 80 – 100 °C) used as internal standard. The contents of the tubes were subjected to heat-catalysed acid transesterification reaction, in a water bath regulated at 80 °C, for 1 h. At the end of the reaction, and after cooling the tubes, 2 mL of n-heptane were added, followed by the addition of 1 mL of deionized water, gently shaking, to ensure an efficient mass transfer between the two phases. The organic phase (of lower density) was collected and filtered through columns containing anhydrous Na₂SO₄, aiming its complete dehydration, and eventually was transferred to appropriate vial for FID-GC analysis. Each sample was processed in quadruplicate.

The content of each vial was analysed in a FID-GC equipment (SCION 436-GC, Bruker, USA, combined with a CP-8400 automatic injector, of the same manufacturer) fitted with a fused-silica capillary column (internal diameter of 0.32 mm and total length of 30 m) internally layered with a polyethylene glycol (PEG) stationary phase (SUPELCOWAX™ 10, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) with a thickness of 0.32 mm, using helium as carrier gas, at a corresponding pressure of 13.5 psi. The injector and detector operate, respectively, at 250 °C and 280 °C, and the column complies a thermal program starting at 200 °C, for 1 min, then increasing at a rate of 2.5 °C/min until 240 °C, remaining at the latter until 22 min of analysis. The split injection system verifies a split ratio of 1:5 and a sampling volume of 0.5 µL.

For the identification of the different peaks detected in each sample, commercial reference standards (GLC-75 and GLC-85 from Nu-Chek-Prep, USA) were simultaneously analysed, and the FAMES identification as done based on the retention time. All chromatograms were obtained and integrated in the Compass CDS software (SCION Instruments, SC).

3.8.3.1. Moisture content

In order to normalise the total FAs results based on a dry basis, it was necessary to determine the moisture content present in each freeze-dried sample, which was carried out gravimetrically by oven-drying at 100 °C, overnight, of a small portion (about 100 mg) of the sample in a porcelain crucible of known oven-dried tare. The analysis was performed in duplicate.

$$\text{Moisture \% } w/w = \frac{w \text{ biomass} - w \text{ dry biomass}}{w \text{ biomass}} \times 100 \quad (17)$$

3.8.3.2. FAs profile

The determination of the FAs profile of each sample started by the individual quantification of each identified FAME. By assumption, knowing the exact mass of internal standard ($w_{IS} = 1 \text{ mg}$), the areas of the peaks referring to a given FA_i and internal standard (A_{FA_i} e A_{IS} , respectively) and the response factor (RF_{FA_i}) that relates the signals of FA_i and internal standard to the same mass, it was possible to quantify each FA_i (w_{FA_i}). Nevertheless, it was considered reasonable to take the value of RF_{FA_i} as unitary, obtaining the following approximation.

$$w_{FA_i} \approx \frac{A_{FA_i}}{A_{IS}} \cdot w_{IS} \quad (18)$$

The mass percentage of each FA_i , could thus be obtained by the following expression.

$$FA_i \% w/w = \frac{w_{FA_i}}{\sum_i^n w_{FA_i}} \quad (19)$$

The characterisation of the FAs profiles also took into account the number of double bonds in the aliphatic chains, by calculating the mass percentages of saturated (SFA), monounsaturated ($MUFA$) and polyunsaturated FAs ($PUFA$).

3.8.3.3. Total FAs contents and titres

For each freeze-dried sample, the mass content of total FAs in dry basis ($Total \text{ FA \% } w/w$) could be determined, as follows.

$$Total \text{ FAs \% } w/w = \frac{\sum_i^n w_{FA_i}}{w \text{ biomass} \cdot (1 - \text{Moisture \% } w/w)} \quad (20)$$

Consequently, it was also possible to approximate the instantaneous titre of intracellular FAs in the culture, [$Total \text{ FAs}$], entering in account with the value of X_{DCW} at the corresponding instant.

$$[Total \text{ FAs}] (t) = X_{DCW}(t) \cdot Total \text{ FAs \% } w/w (t) \quad (21)$$

For the cultures grown in complex hydrolysate, it was necessary to quantify the intrinsic value of $TS \% w/w$ concerning the medium without cells. In this case, the equation (22) was used in order to discount the weight of particles from the weight of the sample taken for the total FAs analysis.

$$Total \text{ FA \% } w/w = \frac{\sum_i^n w_{AG_i}}{w \text{ biomass} \cdot (1 - \text{Moisture \% } w/w) \cdot (1 - TS \% w/w)} \quad (22)$$

3.8.4. Total lipids quantification

The quantification of the total lipid content in the freeze-dried yeast biomass samples was performed using the Soxhlet solid-liquid extraction method. The preparation of each sample began with the cell disruption using a bead mill (MM 400, Retsch®, DE) working at a frequency of 25 s^{-1} , for 3.7 min, with 1 cm diameter metallic beads. The extraction system consisted, from bottom to top, of a heating plate, a distillation flask containing 160 mL of hexane as a non-polar extracting solvent, an extraction chamber in which a single porous thimble containing about 500 mg of previously disrupted yeast biomass was inserted, and a water-cooled Allihn condenser. The extraction was performed for 6 h. Afterwards, the flasks containing the extracted lipid-rich organic solvent were cooled to room temperature. The removal of the extracting solvent, for recovery of extracted lipids, was conducted in a rotary evaporation (Rotavapor® R 110, Büchi, CH, coupled to a Vac® V-500 vacuum pump, of the same brand) with the water bath set at $40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The remaining oil phase in the flask is then incubated at $35\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2 h for total volatilisation of the hexane, and then transferred to a desiccator until constant weight.

3.8.4.1. Total lipids contents and titres

Analogously to FAs, the values of the mass content of total lipids in dry basis, *Total Lipids* % w/w, and the instantaneous titre of intracellular lipids in the culture, [*Total Lipids*], could still be obtained as shown in equations (23) and (25), correspondingly, being although necessary to consider the contribution of *TS* % w/w from the cultures in complex hydrolysates, as shown in equation (24).

$$Total\ Lipids\ \% w/w = \frac{w\ extracted\ lipids}{w\ biomass \cdot (1 - Moisture\ \% w/w)} \quad (23)$$

$$Total\ Lipids\ \% w/w = \frac{w\ extracted\ lipids}{w\ biomass \cdot (1 - Moisture\ \% w/w) \cdot (1 - TS\ \% w/w)} \quad (24)$$

$$[Total\ Lipids](t) = X_{DCW}(t) \cdot Total\ Lipids\ \% w/w(t) \quad (25)$$

3.9. Kjeldahl nitrogen quantification

With the purpose of quantify titrimetrically the nitrogen present in organic and ammoniacal form in different samples, the Kjeldahl method was used, adapted from (Standard Methods Committee of the American Public Health Association; American Water Works Association; Water Environment Federation, 2018), which consists of three stages: mineralisation, distillation, and titration. Likewise the classical method (1883), this procedure presupposes the complete mineralisation of these forms of nitrogen in ammonium sulphate, by the ca: [1] action of sulphuric acid, at high temperatures, according to the following generic reaction.

Thus, for each digestion tube, 50 mL of a digestion reagent composed by 134 g/L K₂SO₄, 20 % v/v concentrated H₂SO₄, and 2.5 % v/v of a catalyst solution (80 g/L HgO in H₂SO₄ 6 N), in an aqueous solution, were transferred. The amount of sample was adjusted in line with the expected Kjeldahl nitrogen content, ranging roughly from 200 mg for nitrogen-rich samples to 13 g for nitrogen-poor samples. For each analyse, a blank test was performed with a nitrogen-free water.

The digestion was executed in a dedicated apparatus (Digestion Unit K-424, Büchi, CH, coupled to a Venturi vacuum system) regulated at maximum power, for the period necessary for the complete clarification of the solution plus additional 30 min, time after which the tubes were cooled to room temperature. To the obtained digest, 100 mL of ultrapure water and 5 drops of 1 g/L phenolphthalein in 95 % v/v ethanol were added, followed by distillation (Distillation Unit K-350, Büchi, CH) of the ammonia from a mixture previously alkalinised with 50 mL of a solution of 500 g/L NaOH and 25 g/L Na₂S₂O₃·5H₂O, according to the reaction below.

The distillate was collected in a 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask containing 50 mL of solution with 20 g/L H₃BO₃ and 1 % v/v indicator mixture (1.33 g/L methyl red and 0.67 g/L methylene blue in 95 % v/v ethanol), for absorption of the ammonia in the form of ammonium ion.

The titration was then carried out with a solution of strong mineral acid, H₂SO₄ at 0.02 N (titrant), until the indicator mixture turned from green to lilac.

In this regard, the total Kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN) could be determined based on the volume of titrant solution dispensed into the sample and blank Erlenmeyer flasks, $\Delta V_{H_2SO_4, 0,02N}(Sample)$ and $\Delta V_{H_2SO_4, 0,02N}(Blank)$, on their normality, $N_{Titrant}$, and on the weight of sample, w_{Sample} , as follows.

$$[TKN] = \frac{\Delta V_{H_2SO_4, 0,02N}(Sample) - \Delta V_{H_2SO_4, 0,02N}(Blank)}{w_{Sample} \cdot 1000} \cdot N \cdot 14,0067 \quad (26)$$

Where 14.0067 is the mass of one nitrogen equivalent, expressed as *gN/eq*.

3.10. Cellular physiological state monitoring

Samples taken throughout the yeast cultivation conducted in the 7L-bioreactor were analysed by FC for viable cell count, using a flow cytometer (Beckman Coulter, CytoFLEX Flow Cytometer, USA) equipped with two solid-state lasers, emitting at 488 and 638 nm, two sensors for detection of light scatter, forward, FSC, and side, SSC, and six fluorescence channels. In this work, FITC detector detecting green fluorescence (525 ± 40 nm), and PC5.5 detector detecting red fluorescence (690 ± 50 nm), were utilised to detect the fluorescence emitted by doubled stained yeast cells with SGI (Thermo Fisher Scientific, SYBR Green I Nucleic Acid Gel Stain, USA) and

PI (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Propidium Iodide, USA). All the light scatter and fluorescence signals were plotted in logarithmic scale cytograms, using CytExpert 2.4 software (Beckman Coulter, USA). The equipment was calibrated daily using a suspension of around 3 μm fluorospheres with an emission range from 410 to 800 nm (Beckman Coulter, CytoFLEX Daily QC Fluorospheres, USA). Ultra-pure water was used as sheath fluid.

All samples, before FC analysis, were subjected to cellular ultrasonic disaggregation (TranssonicT660/H, Elma, DE) for 10 sec, at 35 kHz, followed by vigorous homogenisation to destroy cell aggregates. For control, unstained samples were previously run in the flow cytometer in order to adjust the cell autofluorescence to the first log decade in the fluorescence density plots (FITC versus PC5.5 channels). This procedure improved distinguishing unstained from stained cells, in the plots. The event flux was also adjusted to 800 to 1200 events/s. Whenever necessary, the samples were diluted with PBS solution (Oxoid, UK) in a total volume of 500 μL . Then, the samples were stained with 3 μL of SGI and 1 of μL PI, in that order, and incubated in the darkness for 30 min. Afterwards, the samples were again homogenised in the vortex and analysed in the flow cytometer. Note that SGI and PI were detected in the FITC and PC5.5 channels, respectively.

3.11. Cell observational monitoring

At least once a day, samples collected from the cultures were analysed under an optical microscope, for earlier contamination detection, using a microscope (Olympus, BX60, JP), under 100x, 400x and 1000x magnifications. Whenever a suspected contamination was detected, the sample was plated into MEA slants and incubated for 24 h, to allow contaminant to grow. The results from contaminated cultures were discarded.

3.12. Sterilisation practices

All materials, reagents and culture media were sterilised by moist heat, in a dedicated autoclave (AJC, Uniclave 88, PT), standardising a permanence time of 20 min for general materials, 25 min for culture media up to 1 L volume, and 30 min for the bioreactor containing 2 L volume of medium inside. All objects contaminated with viable cells were properly decontaminated.

3.13. Statistical dispersion

As a measure of dispersion of the experimental replicates, for each result the population standard deviation (σ_p) was calculated using the function STDEV.P, from Excel, which represents the following expression.

$$\sigma_p = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^2}{N}} \quad (27)$$

Where x_i stands for the observed values of the sample, $\bar{x}$ for the mean value of these observations, and N for the total size of the population.

For subsequent calculations, the dispersion was propagated according to the following approximations.

$$\sigma_{x+y} = \sigma_x + \sigma_y \quad (28)$$

$$\sigma_{x-y} = \sigma_x + \sigma_y \quad (29)$$

$$\sigma_{x \times y} \cong \tilde{x}\sigma_y + \tilde{y}\sigma_x \quad (30)$$

$$\frac{\sigma_x}{\tilde{y}} \cong \frac{\sigma_x}{\tilde{y}} - \frac{\tilde{x}\sigma_y}{(\tilde{y})^2} \quad (31)$$

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Screening in CSH-mimic synthetic medium

In the current work, three basidiomycetes yeast strains were compared regarding the ability to accumulate intracellular lipids, with particular interest in the FAs fraction, aiming to valorising CS wastes. In this sense, the responses of these three microorganisms were investigated when cultivated on CSH-mimic synthetic medium for further comparisons with complex CSH+CSL medium cultivations.

4.1.1. Growth and substrates uptake

The substrates uptake and growth profiles for the three yeasts, cultivated on semi-defined CSH-mimic synthetic medium are represented in **Figure 16**.

Figure 16. Comparison of residual sugar and inhibitors concentration, optical density, pH readings, and biomass concentration profiles among the three studied yeast strains: *R. toruloides* (at 30 °C), *T. oleaginosus* (at 30 °C) and *R. babjevae* (at 30 and 25 °C) grown on CSH-mimic synthetic medium, at a scale of 150 mL.

Figure 17 shows the Napierian logarithm of the DCW versus the incubation time.

Figure 17. Napierian logarithm of biomass concentration versus time profiles for the three studied yeast strains: *R. toruloides* (at 30 °C), *T. oleaginosus* (at 30 °C) and *R. babjevae* (at 30 and 25 °C) grown on CSH-mimic synthetic medium, at a scale of 150 mL. Calculation of the μ_{max} parameter.

The growth and substrates uptake kinetic parameters were calculated and summarised in **Table 5**.

Table 5. Comparison of growth and substrates uptake kinetic parameters among the three studied yeast strains: *R. toruloides* (at 30 °C), *T. oleaginosus* (at 30 °C) and *R. babjevae* (at 30 and 25 °C) grown on CSH-mimic synthetic medium, at a scale of 150 mL. Note that the *R. toruloides* was cultivated for a longer period in order to reach the stationary phase.

Parameter	Unit.	<i>R. toruloides</i>	<i>T. oleaginosus</i>	<i>R. babjevae</i> (at 30 °C)	<i>R. babjevae</i> (at 25 °C)
Cultivation period	h	95.8	70.6	71.3	70.7
Growth kinetic parameters:					
$X_{DCW\ max}$	g_{DCW}/L	23.80 ± 1.09 (71.7 h)	35.62 ± 0.95 (46.4 h)	8.55 ± 0.38 (71.3 h)	10.08 ± 0.18 (27.8 h)
$X_{DCW\ final}$	g_{DCW}/L	21.31 ± 2.13	33.30 ± 0.28	8.55 ± 0.38	9.75 ± 0.36

Prod _{vol} (X) _{global}	g _{DCW} /L /h	0.216 ± 0.027	0.455 ± 0.006	0.108 ± 0.006	0.128 ± 0.006
Prod _{vol} (X) _{max}	g _{DCW} /L /h	0.435 ± 0.005	0.839 ± 0.013	0.321 ± 0.000	0.382 ± 0.009
μ _{max}	h ⁻¹	0.098 ± 0.003	0.125 ± 0.000	0.099 ± 0.000	0.119 ± 0.004
Y _{X/S}	g _{DCW} /g	0.246 ± 0.027	0.406 ± 0.002	0.244 ± 0.003	0.277 ± 0.002
Substrates uptake kinetic parameters:					
-r _{Glucose,max}	g/L/h	1.28 ± 0.14	2.25 ± 0.05	0.63 ± 0.02	0.89 ± 0.05
-r _{Xylose,max}	g/L/h	0.32 ± 0.03	0.63 ± 0.02	0.27 ± 0.03	0.02 ± 0.02
-r _{Acetic acid,max}	g/L/h	0.12 ± 0.01	0.15 ± 0.01	0.12 ± 0.01	0.13 ± 0.00
-r _{Formic acid, max}	g/L/h	0.02 ± 0.00	0.03 ± 0.00	-	-
-r _{Glucose,global}	g/L/h	0.68 ± 0.01	0.844 ± 0.01	0.37 ± 0.01	0.45 ± 0.02
-r _{Xylose,global}	g/L/h	0.20 ± 0.00	0.278 ± 0.01	0.07 ± 0.01	0.01 ± 0.00
-r _{Acetic acid,global}	g/L/h	0.03 ± 0.00	0.037 ± 0.00	0.04 ± 0.00	0.04 ± 0.00
-r _{Formic acid, global}	g/L/h	0.01 ± 0.00	0.010 ± 0.00	-	-

Regarding cell growth, there was a variability of behaviour among the studied yeast strains. However, according to the **Figure 16**, in all cases, growth was observed with an insignificant lag phase, except for *R. babjevae* at 25 °C whose LN(X_{DCW}) versus time growth curve is inconclusive. In turn, this fact corroborates the high robustness of all the strains to the presence of high initial concentrations of total sugars, which ranged from 73.5 ± 0.8 to 89.5 ± 1.0 g/L, and in the presence of trace inhibitory compounds, in particular, HMF and furfural which were detected in concentrations ranging from 0.025 ± 0.000 to 0.035 ± 0.000 g/L and 0.023 ± 0.005 to 0.157 ± 0.001 g/L, respectively. This observation was predicted, since comparable sugar compositions had already been successfully studied, with a concentration of total sugars of 78.5 g/L (52.8 g/L glucose and 25.7 g/L xylose) for *R. babjevae* DBVPG 8058 and *R. toruloides* CBS 14 on WSH (Brandenburg, et al., 2021) and 83.73 g/L (51.28 g/L glucose and 32.45 g/L xylose), for *T. oleaginosus* DSM 11815 on corn cobs hydrolysate (Grubišić, et al., 2022). Besides, this *T. oleaginosus* strain was grown at HMF and furfural concentrations of 0.44 g/L (Yu, Zheng, Dorgan, & Chen, 2011) and 3 g/L (Yu, Zeng, Zheng, & Chen, 2014), respectively, whereas *R. toruloides* NRRL Y-1091 showed high tolerance to these components up to 0.50 g/L and 0.77 g/L (Liu, Fels, Dragone, & Mussatto, 2021), albeit both with diminished performance. *R. toruloides*-1588 was also studied for assimilating up to 3 g/L of furfural (Osorio-González, Saini, Hegde, Brar, & Avalos Ramirez, 2022). Scarce publications were found referring the tolerance of *R. babjevae* to these compounds. However, a study published in 2014 confirmed the tolerance of two strains, UCDFST 04-877 and 05-775, to HMF at concentrations up to 1 and 2 g/L, respectively, while no growth was found for the range of furfural concentrations studied (0.5 to 1 g/L) (Sitepu, Selby, Lin, Zhu, & Boundy-Mills, 2014).

The exponential growth phase lasted approximately 24 h for the four experiments, with *T. oleaginosus* standing out with a μ_{max} value of 0.125 h⁻¹, compared to 0.098 h⁻¹, 0.099 h⁻¹, and 0.119 h⁻¹ achieved by the candidates *R.*

toruloides, and *R. babjevae* grown at 30 and 25 °C, respectively. After this period, an apparent deceleration phase was observed for *T. oleaginosus* and *R. toruloides*, which could most likely be associated with oxygen limitation condition (usually present in shake flasks cultivations), finally entering the stationary phase until the end of the experiments.

Firstly, oxygen limitation occurs when the DO value in the media becomes lower than the $DO_{critical}$, which is rather common in aerobic cultures given the low solubility of this gas at the optimal cultivation temperatures for oleaginous yeasts (25 to 30 °C), and the high cell densities typically reached (Liu S. , 2017). Unlike the soluble nutrients, oxygen is never totally depleted in microbial cultures developed in shake flasks, and its limitation will only affect the growth rate, never stopping growth while the other nutrients are present in excess, which is in line with the behaviours of *T. oleaginosus* and *R. toruloides*, since in both cultivations the deceleration phase started when glucose and xylose concentrations were higher than 50 % of its initial value, and the DCW almost doubled during this phase.

From another perspective, it would also be possible that this increase in DCW was due to the accumulation of intracellular lipids instead of cell growth, since the DCW quantification method does not distinguish cell mass from lipid mass, and although some oleaginous yeasts may show a higher increase in lipid content during the exponential phase (Michely, Gaillardin, Nicaud, & Neuvéglise, 2013; Freitas, et al., 2014), typically, for most oleaginous yeasts including *T. oleaginosus* DSM 11815 lipid accumulation is more expressive during the stationary phase (i Nogué, et al., 2018). To confirm this hypothesis, it would be necessary to determine the lipid accumulation profile over the cultivation time, which is not possible at this scale, since lipid and FAs analysis requires considerable amounts of freeze-dried biomass.

Unexpectedly, and contrarily to *R. toruloides* and *T. oleaginosus* cultivations, *R. babjevae* cultivated at 30 and 25 °C entered the stationary phase just after the exponential growth phase ended without depleting the carbon sources. For each corresponding temperature (25 °C and 30 °C) only 45.8 % and 57.1 % of glucose and 23.5 % and 3.3 % of xylose, respectively, were consumed at the end of the cultivations. Besides, DCW reached the maximum values of 8.6 ± 0.4 and 10.1 ± 0.2 g_{DCW}/L , respectively. These results seemed quite surprising, considering the reported remarkable DCW values of 28.02 ± 2.30 g_{DCW}/L , when the yeast was grown on 350-mL WSH, at 25 °C, after 96 h (Brandenburg, et al., 2021), or 16.48 ± 0.40 g_{DCW}/L , when grown on 350-mL WSH, at 30 °C, after 40 h (Brandenburg, et al., 2018), having depleted the carbon sources in both assays. Thereby, the results obtained for *R. babjevae* experiments suggest possible inhibition either by a primary metabolite, e.g., a product of inhibitors degradation, a decrease in the medium pH, by promoting short-chain organic acid inhibiting, or a nutrient depletion.

In fact, after almost 24 h of cultivation, at 30 °C, the medium pH of *R. babjevae* cultures attained the value of 4.69, with concentrations of 0.07 ± 0.04 g/L of acetic acid and 0.64 ± 0.05 g/L of formic acid, and similarly, in the essays conducted at 25 °C, after 24 h, the pH value was 5.00, with concentrations of 0.10 ± 0.00 g/L and 0.65 ± 0.00 g/L of the same acids. Given the pK_a values (at 25 °C) of 4.76 and 3.75 for acetic and formic acids (Serjeant & B., 1979; Riddick, 1986), respectively, and applying the Henderson-Hasselbalch equation, 53 % of the acetic

acid, and 10 % of formic acid were undissociated, which are toxic for yeasts, as discussed in 1.2.1.1 section. Therefore, *R. babjevae* cells metabolism inhibition by organic acids could explain the observations above reported. At the end of the cultivations, the medium pH values of 3.93 and 4.00 were recorded at 30 and 25 °C, respectively, without any consumption of formic acid (as formate), with the fraction of the undissociated form reaching up to 41%, even though all the acetic acid was almost depleted. Given its low pK_a and molecular size, formic acid is considered even more toxic than acetic acid, since it may diffuse more easily across the plasmatic membrane and, upon reaching the cytosol, it becomes mostly in the dissociated form (Oshoma, et al., 2015), threatening cell structures and metabolism, as also discussed in 1.2.1.1 section. Still, an additional study at higher and constant pH would be necessary to validate this hypothesis.

On the other hand, inhibition by a primary metabolite is not excluded since both HMF and furfural were detected in low concentrations since the first instants of cultivation, which was observed for all cultivation assays and not for control assays. Previous studies with *T. oleaginosus* DSM 11815 confirmed the detoxification of HMF into 5-HMF alcohol and 5-HMF acid, a pathway which, according to the authors, may be transposable to furfural, given their structural similarities, producing compounds such as furfuryl alcohol or furoic acid (i Nogué, et al., 2018; Wang, Gao, Zhang, & Bao, 2016). Although this mechanism may be variable between different strains of oleaginous yeast, the observed depletion of these two furans strongly supports the idea that acids and alcohols derived from them may have been synthesised. In certain cases, these compounds may be more toxic than the original molecules, as in the example of *T. fermentans* CICC 1368 which has previously shown a greater susceptibility to furfuryl alcohol than furfural. This strain was grown on rich synthetic medium containing alcohol inhibitors and showed sugar consumption inhibition, damages to cell membranes, and growth and lipid accumulation hindering, most likely due to malic enzyme inhibition (Huang, Wu, Liu, Lou, & Zong, 2012). In this sense, further studies monitoring the physiological state of *R. babjevae* cell cultures, namely, the enzymatic activity or membrane integrity via FC would be needed to support this suspicion.

Finally, the depletion of an essential macro or micronutrient after 24 h of cultivation of *R. babjevae* could explain a sudden entrance of this strain in the stationary phase, according to the Monod equation. Regarding the nutritional composition, it should be noted that the formulations in the above-mentioned studies were slightly different, being in one case 1.7 g/L of YNB (without amino acids and ammonium sulphate), 2 g/L of $(NH_4)_2SO_4$ and 0.75 g/L of yeast extract (Brandenburg, et al., 2018), and in another 1.7 g/L of YNB (without amino acids and ammonium sulphate), 0.5 g/L of $MgSO_4$ and 2 g/L of $(NH_4)_3PO_4$ (Brandenburg, et al., 2021), besides, in both works the carbon source was provided by WSH rather than a synthetic mixture, such may contain several other nutrients. However, it is not evident that the medium used by the referred authors is nutritionally richer than the one used in the present work, since the last one contained 6.7 g/L of YNB (with amino acids and ammonium sulphate), which is equivalent to concentrations in the media of 5 g/L of $(NH_4)_2SO_4$, 0.5 g/L of essential amino acids, 1 g/L KH_2PO_4 , and 0.5 g/L $MgSO_4$, among other components. Thus, although the composition of the yeast extract used by (Brandenburg, et al., 2018) is unknown, everything indicates that the formulation in the present study is richer, except for the phosphate ions which is higher in Brandenburg, et al.

(2021) work, not being proved this hypothesis. Accordingly, additional experiments with increased concentrations of different nutrients would be needed.

In previous studies, *R. babjevae* was grown at 25 °C (Brandenburg, et al., 2021; Shapaval, et al., 2019). In the present study, nevertheless, this strain was grown at 30 °C and 25 °C aiming to assess the effect of temperature on cell growth and FAs accumulation. Indeed, when cultivated at 25 °C, and maintaining all the other conditions, the growth performance of this yeast was improved with a μ_{max} 1.2-fold higher its value at 30 °C, and an increment of 1.54 g_{DCW}/L in maximum DCW. Biomass volumetric productivities and yield coefficient referring to the total sugars were also meaningfully enhanced. Two possible explanations for this observation may be the significant increase in the oxygen solubility in the medium, with the temperature decrease, from 8.05 mg/L at 30 °C to 8.69 mg/L at 25 °C (Mass Transfer, 2013), considering pure water under 1 atm air pressure as approximation to the culture medium, or an increase in the activity of enzymes involved in cell division, assuming that 25°C is the optimal temperature for *R. babjevae* growth.

Regarding the sugars uptake profiles, all the studied strains at 30 °C showed the ability to consume both sugars simultaneously, although with a notable preference for glucose, which was already predicted for these three yeasts (Brandenburg J. , et al., 2021; Shaigani P. , et al., 2021; Martins, et al., 2021) and could be due both to a carbon catabolite repression phenomenon and to an allosteric competition between the transport proteins involved in the internalisation of these sugars (Kim, Block, & Mills, 2010). In particular, after about 24 h *R. toruloides*, *T. oleaginosus*, and *R. babjevae* cultivations at 30 °C and 25 °C showed xylose consumption percentages of 17 %, 18 %, 19 % and 0 % against glucose consumption percentages of 29 %, 47 %, 23 % and 32 % respectively. Interestingly, for *R. babjevae* conducted at 25 °C there was no appreciable consumption of xylose, contrasting with a higher consumption of glucose compared to the same strain grown at 30 °C, which could hypothetically indicate an inhibition of the enzymes involved in xylose catabolism or transport through the membrane in this yeast at 25 °C. For *R. toruloides* and *T. oleaginosus*, correspondingly, $-r_{glucose,max}$ values of 1.28 ± 0.14 g/L/h and 2.25 ± 0.05 g/L/h were estimated at the end of exponential phase, and $-r_{xylose,max}$ values of 0.32 ± 0.03 g/L/h and 0.63 ± 0.02 g/L/h reached after glucose depletion, meaning a much higher consumption efficiency of the two sugars for the second yeast. Less relevant values were estimated for *R. babjevae* with a $-r_{glucose,max}$ of 0.63 ± 0.02 g/L/h at 30 °C and 0.89 ± 0.05 g/L/h at 25 °C, and a $-r_{xylose,max}$ of 0.11 ± 0.03 g/L/h at 30 °C, both during the exponential growth phase.

A quite variable behaviour was observed for the organic acids uptake profiles, being the acetic acid preferably uptaken over formic acid, and simultaneously, for *R. toruloides* and *T. oleaginosus*, and the formic acid not consumed by *R. babjevae*, as discussed before. Similar profiles were previously obtained for *T. oleaginosus* DSM 11815 (Liang, Jarosz, & Wardlow, 2014; Broos, et al., 2022). Moreover, in all the studied yeasts, glucose and acetic acid (as acetate) were consumed simultaneously, a fact that has also been observed by other authors (Brandenburg, et al., 2021; Lopes, Bonturi, & Miranda, 2020; Broos, et al., 2022), suggesting that in these strains glucose catabolism also does not promotes catabolite repression neither allosteric inhibition on acetic acid.

Overall, *T. oleaginosus* emerged in the present work as the fastest and most efficient oleaginous yeast growing on the semi-defined CSH-mimic synthetic medium, leading to an impressive DCW of 33.30 ± 0.28 g_{DCW}/L after 71.6 h of cultivation, corresponding to a global biomass volumetric productivity value of 0.455 ± 0.006 g_{DCW}/L/h, even under possible oxygen supply limitation which often occurs in cultures developed in shake-flasks or the absence of control of important operating parameters such as pH. This strain also showed to be the most efficient in converting sugars into biomass with a $Y_{X/S}$ value of 0.406 ± 0.002 g_{DCW}/g. The present work displayed even better results of biomass concentration and biomass productivity than those reported by Yu, Zheng, Xiong, & Chen (2014), who reported 30.6 ± 1.6 g_{DCW}/L and 0.255 ± 0.013 g_{DCW}/L/h, respectively, obtained after the yeast cultivation on a synthetic medium containing 56 g/L of glucose and 14 g/L of xylose for 120 h. These results might be due to the presence of extra carbon and energy sources such as acetate and formate (Lian, Garcia-Perez, Coates, Wu, & Chen, 2012), giving the higher $Y_{X/S}$ value of 0.439 ± 0.033 g_{DCW}/g (Yu, Zheng, Xiong, & Chen, 2014) comparing to $Y_{X/S}$ obtained for *T. oleaginosus* cultures developed in the present culture (0.406 ± 0.002 g_{DCW}/g), or to more favourable growth conditions. Still, *R. toruloides* achieved reasonable values of DCW and a global biomass volumetric productivity of 21.31 ± 2.13 g_{DCW}/L and 0.216 ± 0.027 g_{DCW}/L/h, respectively, after 95.8 h of cultivation, although still below from a previous work performed on WSH for *R. toruloides* CBS 14 with correspondent values of 29.82 ± 0.25 g_{DCW}/L and 0.328 ± 0.003 g_{DCW}/L/h, after 91 h of cultivation (Brandenburg, et al., 2021). Unpredictably, *R. babjevae* showed poor results, with a final DCW of around one third of that obtained in the same study conducted on WSH, after 96 h of cultivation, leading to conclude that this strain did not reveal its typical growth behaviour in the present work, for the reasons already mentioned.

4.1.2. Intracellular lipids accumulation

In **Figure 18** the mass contents of Total FAs and Total Lipids, on a DCW basis, as well as the respective titres in the final culture broth, in g/L, are shown for each of studied yeast.

Figure 18. Comparison of Total FAs and Lipids contents, in % w/w of DCW, and its titres, in g/L, at the final instants of cultivation among the three studied yeast strains: *R. toruloides* (at 30 °C), *T. oleaginosus* (at 30 °C) and *R. babjevae* (at 30 °C and 25 °C) grown on CSH-mimic synthetic medium, at a scale of 150 mL.

Converging, therefore, the obtained data with growth and substrates uptake kinetics it is also possible to obtain the kinetic parameters for intracellular lipids' accumulation, which are presented in **Table 6**.

Table 6. Comparison of intracellular lipids accumulation kinetic parameters among the three studied yeast strains: *R. toruloides* (at 30 °C), *T. oleaginosus* (at 30 °C) and *R. babjevae* (at 30 °C and 25 °C) grown on CSH-mimic synthetic medium, at a scale of 150 mL.

Parameter	Unit.	<i>R. toruloides</i>	<i>T. oleaginosus</i>	<i>R. babjevae</i> (at 30 °C)	<i>R. babjevae</i> (at 25 °C)
Cultivation period	h	95.8	70.6	71.3	70.7
Prod _{Vol} (FAS) _{global}	g _{FAS} /L/h	0.061 ± 0.012	0.113 ± 0.005	0.014 ± 0.000	0.014 ± 0.001
Prod _{Vol} (L) _{global}	g _L /L/h	0.081 ± 0.009	0.119 ± 0.001	0.025 ± 0.000	0.025 ± 0.001
Y _{FAS/S}	g _{FAS} /g	0.070 ± 0.013	0.101 ± 0.003	0.032 ± 0.000	0.031 ± 0.001
Y _{L/S}	g _L /g	0.092 ± 0.009	0.106 ± 0.001	0.056 ± 0.002	0.053 ± 0.001

The FAs profiles and, consequently, the SFA, MUFA and PUFA contents were also determined, as shown in **Figure 19**.

Figure 19. Comparison of FAs profiles, in % w/w of Total FAs, and the SFA, MUFA and PUFA contents, in % w/w of Total FAs, at the final instants of cultivation among the three studied yeast strains: *R. toruloides* (at 30 °C), *T. oleaginosus* (at 30 °C) and *R. babjevae* (at 30 and 25 °C) grown on CSH-mimic synthetic medium, at a scale of 150 mL.

At first glance, *R. toruloides* stood out as the most efficient strain with notable lipids and FAs mass contents of $36.2 \pm 0.5 \%$ and $27.6 \pm 2.8 \%$, in a DCW basis, correspondingly, although *T. oleaginosus* showed the highest lipids and FAs titres of $8.4 \pm 0.1 \text{ g/L}$ and $8.0 \pm 0.4 \text{ g/L}$, by the same order, due to a better growth performance. In this regard, an above-mentioned study using *R. toruloides* CBS 14 grown on WSH reported similar results with a lipid mass content after 96 h reaching $39.31 \pm 2.65 \%$, on a DCW basis, corresponding to a lipid titre of $11.72 \pm 0.64 \text{ g/L}$ (Brandenburg J. , et al., 2021). For *T. oleaginosus*, however, the obtained values seem to be lower than the predicted, considering several studies reporting lipid mass contents of around 60 %, 58 % and 53 % of DCW on sorghum stalk, switchgrass, and microalgal hydrolysates (Lee, Vadlani, & Min, 2017; Meo, Laura Priebe, & Weuster-Botz, 2017) or a total FAs mass content of $63.1 \pm 3.7 \%$ of DCW on corn stover hydrolysate (i Nogué, et al., 2018). In the previously mentioned study on corn cobs hydrolysate, a lipid mass content of 39.15 % was estimated, corresponding to a lipid titre of 18.97 g/L (Grubišić, et al., 2022), values also higher than those obtained in the present work. However, these differences could arise from the respective composition of inhibitory compounds, such as phenolics that have already proved to be an efficient substrate for lipid accumulation in this strain (Yaguchi, Robinson, Mihealsick, & Blenner, 2017), and total sugars, since the cited articles used complex hydrolysates, as well as from other operational parameters such as pH, stirring speed, temperature, cultivation period, nutrient ratios, among others. An already referred study using a synthetic medium containing 56 g/L glucose and 14 g/L xylose also yielded a higher lipid mass content of $39.8 \pm 1.8 \%$ of DCW, after 120 h of cultivation (Yu, Zheng, Xiong, & Chen, 2014). Other experiments conducted on synthetic medium also revealed higher lipid contents (Bracharz, Beukhout, Mehlmer, & Brück, 2017), however, due to the absence of inhibitors in its formulations, few conclusions can be drawn.

Few differences were found for *R. babjevae* when cultivated at both 25 °C and 30 °C. The latter temperature promoted slightly higher lipid and FAs contents of $20.7 \pm 0.0 \%$ and $11.7 \pm 0.0 \%$ against $17.8 \pm 0.1 \%$ and $10.5 \pm 0.5 \%$ at 25 °C. In other words, a decrease in the cultivation temperature was mirrored in an improvement in growth along with a decrease in the lipid content, which had been observed before for *Cryptococcus gilvescens* DBVPG 4714, a facultative psychrophilic yeast (Rossi, et al., 2009). A feasible hypothesis for this result could reside in the negligible consumption of xylose noted at 25 °C, since it has already been observed that xylose assimilation plays an important role in lipid accumulation (Brandenburg, et al., 2021), probably due to the involvement of the phosphoketolase pathway which yields 9.7 g of Acetyl-CoA from 100 g of xylose, comparing to the 8.9 g produced from 100 g of glucose (Shaigani P. , et al., 2021). In this regard, it is known that xylose could theoretically yield about 0.34 g lipids / g of sugar, a higher value when compared with glucose with a yield of 0.32 g lipids / g of sugar, for some oleaginous microorganisms (Papanikolaou & Aggelis, 2011). Nevertheless, previous publications for *R. babjevae* DBVPG 8058 grown at 25 and 30 °C do not allow inferring any correlation between temperature and lipid content (Brandenburg, et al., 2018; Brandenburg, et al., 2021). Generally, given that by convention only those organisms that can accumulate more than 20 % of their DCW in intracellular lipids are considered to be oleaginous (Ratledge & Wynn, 2002), it can be concluded that the performance of this microorganism does not meet the requirements for the desired process under the studied conditions. Further optimisation studies would be necessary to figure out the reasons for the unviability of this

strain in the studied synthetic medium, as discussed yet. Additionally, despite the lower content of lipids accumulated at 25 °C, it was considered that this temperature would confer more advantages for future works in line with pre-existing literature where this strain revealed an excellent performance when compared with other well-known oleaginous yeasts such as *R. glutinis* CBS 2367, *R. toruloides* CBS 14, *Lipomyces starkeyi* CBS 1807 and *L. starkeyi* CBS 7544 (Brandenburg, et al., 2021).

Despite of high lipid content attained by *R. toruloides*, the volumetric lipid productivity is of critical importance for the selection of the optimum oleaginous strain, for subsequent scale-up step, considering that a significant reduction in the cultivation time will lead to a higher profitability of this bioprocess (Karlsson, et al., 2016), minimising both the consumption of industrial utilities such as compressed air, refrigeration fluids or direct electricity for agitation and heating, and also the consumption of reagents such as acid, base or anti-foaming agent. In this sense, *T. oleaginosus* achieved remarkable volumetric productivities in lipids and FAs of 0.119 ± 0.001 g_L/L/h and 0.113 ± 0.005 g_{FAs}/L/h, respectively, values almost 50 % above than those for the opponent *R. toruloides*, which required extra 25.2 h to reach comparable lipids and FAs titres. These values for lipids are even higher than the 0.097 g_L/L/h observed for a WSH supplemented with CSL, after 72 h of cultivation (Shaigani, et al., 2021), and the 0.101 g_L/L/h estimated for a synthetic medium containing 56 g/L of glucose and 14 g/L of xylose, after 120 h of cultivation (Yu, Zheng, Xiong, & Chen, 2014).

Because of its highest values of lipid titre and sugar consumption percentage in the present search, *T. oleaginosus* also stood out from the opponents with $Y_{L/S}$ and $Y_{FAs/S}$ of 0.106 ± 0.001 g_L/g and 0.101 ± 0.003 g_{FAs}/g, correspondingly, which means that for each kg of lipids to be produced, around 7.07 kg of glucose and 2.36 kg of xylose (9.42 kg of total sugars) would be needed, in this conditions. In previous studies with synthetic medium, slightly higher $Y_{L/S}$ values of 0.19 g_L/g and 0.20 g_L/g had been observed in synthetic medium containing exclusively 30 g/L of glucose and 30 g/L of xylose, respectively, after 72 h of growth (Shaigani, et al., 2021). An equally higher $Y_{L/S}$ value of 0.175 ± 0.021 g_L/g was observed in the mentioned study using 56 g/L of glucose and 14 g/L of xylose as carbon sources (Yu, Zheng, Xiong, & Chen, 2014), which could be explained by the absence of inhibitors in its formulations. The absence of inhibitors in the formulation of these synthetic media could seem the most obvious reason for the variations in results. However, studies performed on complex hydrolysates revealed values also higher, e.g., 0.19 g_L/g when cultivated on WSH supplemented with CSL, at a scale of 100 mL in shake-flasks (Shaigani, et al., 2021).

Considering that the produced MOs must be suitable for biolubricants and bio-based PUs, a more detailed comparative analysis of the FAs profile among the different strains was also done. At first reading, it is notable that C 16:0, C 18:0, C 18:1 ω-9, C 18:2 ω-6 and C 18:3 ω-3 acids, made up the majority of the FAs accumulated for all the studied microorganisms, being the C 18:1 ω-9 the one that stands out most among the others. Itself, C 18:1 ω-9 acid appears with mass contents, on a total FAs basis, of 51.7 ± 0.3 %, 48.3 ± 0.1 %, 57.2 ± 0.0 % and 49.9 ± 0.0 %, for the yeasts *R. toruloides*, *T. oleaginosus* and *R. babjevae* at 30 °C and at 25 °C, respectively, values, for instance, of the order of magnitude usually reported for peanut or rapeseed oils (Coles, 2013). Similar C 18:1 ω-9 mass fractions have been reported, e.g., 46.53 ± 0.65 % for *R. toruloides* NCYC 921 on

synthetic medium containing 29.4 g/L glucose and 3.6 g/L xylose at 30 °C, after 72 h (Martins, et al., 2021), or 41.2 ± 1.9 % for *T. oleaginosus* DSM 11815 on synthetic medium containing 56 g/L glucose and 14 g/L xylose at 30 °C, after 120 h (Yu, Zheng, Xiong, & Chen, 2014), however, a lower value of 23.3 ± 0.9 % was found for *R. babjevae* DBVPG 8058 on WSH at 30 °C, after 40 h (Brandenburg, et al., 2018). In second place was C 16:0 acid with mass percentages of 23.4 ± 0.1 %, 29.1 ± 0.0 %, 16.4 ± 0.0 % and 19.0 ± 0.0 %, by the same order, a range of values similar to that reported for cottonseed oil (Coles, 2013).

By comparison, C 16:0 acid mass fractions of 13.14 ± 0.28 %, 33.0 ± 0.2 % and 10.3 ± 0.7 %, were determined, correspondingly, for *R. toruloides* NCYC 921, *T. oleaginosus* DSM 11815 and *R. babjevae* DBVPG 8058, in the above-mentioned publications (Freitas, et al., 2014; Yu, Zheng, Xiong, & Chen, 2014; Brandenburg, et al., 2018), values slightly dispersed when compared with those obtained in the present work, which may be due, among other factors, to different cultivation conditions and different stages of lipid accumulation represented. Previous studies also demonstrated the ability of the strain *R. babjevae* DBVPG 8058 to accumulate significant amounts of minor FAs, namely, heptadecenoic acid (C 17:1 ω -7) and C 18:3 ω -6, being the first known for its anti-inflammatory and edema-inhibiting properties and the latter an important dietary supplement and anti-inflammatory (Brandenburg, et al., 2018; Řezanka, Kolouchová, & Sigler, 2015; Choopani, Poorsoltan, Fazilati, Latifi, & Salavati, 2016), however, in the present study, vestigial fractions was found for C 17:1 and no C 18:3 ω -6 was detected.

It is curious that *T. oleaginosus* showed the highest SFAs mass fraction of 42.8 ± 0.0 % followed by *R. toruloides* and *R. babjevae* at 25 °C and at 30 °C, with corresponding SFAs mass fractions of 38.3 ± 0.4 %, 26.3 ± 0.1 % and 25.3 ± 0.1 % on a total FAs basis. Concerning the mass fractions of MUFAs, *R. babjevae* at 30 °C outstood with a value of 59.9 ± 0.0 %, followed by the same strain grown at 25 °C, *R. toruloides* and finally *T. oleaginosus* with correspondent values of 53.5 ± 0.1 %, 52.8 ± 0.3 % and 48.9 ± 0.0 %. Interestingly, *R. babjevae* revealed the highest PUFAs mass fractions among the studied strains with values of 14.8 ± 0.2 % at 30 °C and 20.2 ± 0.0 % at 25 °C, relatively lower when confronted with the value of 23.34 ± 0.67 % previously obtained at 30 °C (Brandenburg, et al., 2021). Furthermore, it should be noted that the decrease in the cultivation temperature, from 30 °C to 25 °C, promoted both a decrease in *R. babjevae* lipid content and an increase in the degree of unsaturation of the accumulated lipids, similarly to the behaviour already observed for *R. toruloides* (Suutari, Liukkonen, & Laakso, 1990). In general, the variation of the lipid profile with temperature has been described as an adaptive mechanism of cellular metabolism to maintain the membrane physical state and functionality over a wider thermal range (Brandenburg, et al., 2018; Rossi, et al., 2009).

4.2. Screening in CSH + CSL complex medium

In order to support the conclusions drawn in section 4.1, the same three oleaginous yeast strains were cultivated on complex medium containing CSH supplemented with CSL and mineral medium, while

maintaining all operating conditions. It should be reinforced that in this set of tests it was decided to perform *R. babjevae* cultivations only at 25 °C.

4.2.1. Growth and substrates uptake

The substrates uptake and growth profiles for the three yeasts, cultivated on complex CSH + CSL medium are displayed in **Figure 20**.

Figure 20. Comparison of residual sugar and inhibitors concentration, optical density, pH readings, and biomass concentration profiles among the three studied yeast strains: *R. toruloides* (at 30 °C), *T. oleaginosus* (at 30 °C) and *R. babjevae* (at 25 °C) grown on complex CSH + CSL medium, at a scale of 150 mL.

Similarly to the section 4.1, the growth curves for each studied oleaginous yeast strain were plotted, as the variation of the Napierian logarithm of the DCW with the incubation time (**Figure 21**).

Figure 21. Napierian logarithm of biomass concentration versus time profiles for the three studied yeast strains: *R. toruloides* (at 30 °C), *T. oleaginosus* (at 30 °C) and *R. babjevae* (at 25 °C) grown on complex CSH + CSL medium, at a scale of 150 mL. Calculation of the μ_{max} parameter.

Analogously to section 4.1, the kinetic parameters for each of the studied yeast strains were calculated and displayed in **Table 7**.

Table 7. Comparison of growth and substrates uptake kinetic parameters among the three studied yeast strains: *R. toruloides* (at 30 °C), *T. oleaginosus* (at 30 °C) and *R. babjevae* (at 25 °C) grown on complex CSH + CSL medium, at a scale of 150 mL.

Parameter	Unit.	<i>R. toruloides</i>	<i>T. oleaginosus</i>	<i>R. babjevae</i>
Cultivation period	h	47.1	47.1	88.9
Growth kinetic parameters:				
X_{DCW} max	g _{DCW} /L	20.34 ± 0.81 (47.1 h)	27.48 ± 0.58 (47.1 h)	12.95 ± 0.86 (66.1 h)
X_{DCW} final	g _{DCW} /L	20.34 ± 0.81	27.48 ± 0.58	11.54 ± 1.46
Prod_{vol}(X_{DCW})_{global}	g _{DCW} /L /h	0.339 ± 0.021	0.488 ± 0.016	0.085 ± 0.025
Prod_{vol}(X_{DCW})_{max}	g _{DCW} /L /h	0.416 ± 0.038	0.510 ± 0.023	0.136 ± 0.001

μ_{max}	h^{-1}	0.051 ± 0.003	0.054 ± 0.001	0.062 ± 0.005
$Y_{X/S}$	g_{DCW}/g	0.283 ± 0.008	0.389 ± 0.003	0.286 ± 0.058
Substrates uptake kinetic parameters:				
$-r_{Glucose,max}$	$g/L/h$	1.12 ± 0.09	1.37 ± 0.05	0.73 ± 0.10
$-r_{Xylose,max}$	$g/L/h$	1.57 ± 0.17	0.93 ± 0.81	0.06 ± 0.04
$-r_{Acetic\ acid,max}$	$g/L/h$	0.15 ± 0.01	0.16 ± 0.01	0.10 ± 0.00
$-r_{Formic\ acid,max}$	$g/L/h$	0.03 ± 0.00	0.09 ± 0.01	-
$-r_{Lactic\ acid,max}$	$g/L/h$	0.03 ± 0.01	0.03 ± 0.00	0.03 ± 0.00
$-r_{Glucose,global}$	$g/L/h$	0.85 ± 0.03	0.85 ± 0.03	0.27 ± 0.02
$-r_{Xylose,global}$	$g/L/h$	0.35 ± 0.08	0.41 ± 0.02	0.03 ± 0.01
$-r_{Acetic\ acid,global}$	$g/L/h$	0.06 ± 0.00	0.060 ± 0.00	0.03 ± 0.00
$-r_{Formic\ acid,global}$	$g/L/h$	0.02 ± 0.00	0.020 ± 0.00	-
$-r_{Lactic\ acid,global}$	$g/L/h$	0.02 ± 0.00	0.023 ± 0.00	0.01 ± 0.00

Based on the growth and substrates uptake profiles outlined in section 4.1.1, several differences were found when the studied yeasts were cultivated on CSH + CSL medium, which is due not only to the significantly lower sugar composition, by the decrease of about 20 g/L of glucose compared to the semi-defined synthetic medium, but also by the additional presence of other undetected compounds in the CSH that were not considered in its formulation, such as levulinic acid, propionic acid, 4-Hydroxybenzoic acid, vanillin, catechol, among others, frequently found in lignocellulosic hydrolysates (Palmqvist & Hahn-Hägerdal, 2000).

In particular, the addition of CSL as a low-cost nitrogen supplement represents itself an important modification comparing with the YNB used in 4.1, since compounds such as lactic acid or starch have a relevant portion in the composition of this by-product (Azizi-Shotorkhoft, Sharifi, Mirmohammadi, Baluch-Gharaei, & Rezaei, 2016). In the present work, at the start of cultivation, between 1.17 ± 0.02 g/L and 1.29 ± 0.05 g/L of lactic acid were quantified, which underwent consumptions of 61 %, 84 % and 65 % for *R. toruloides*, *T. oleaginosus* and *R. babjevae*, respectively. This observation was not unique since *R. toruloides* IFO0880 had already been described for its ability to co-consume lactic acid at concentrations of 21 g/L (Sundstrom, et al., 2018), while other oleaginous yeasts such as *Yarrowia lipolytica*, *T. oleaginosus*, or *Rhodotorula glutinis* also proved to be able to assimilate this compound (Johnravindar, Karthikeyan, Selvam, Murugesan, & Wong, 2018). Previous catabolic studies for *Y. lipolytica* have shown that both the L and D enantiomers of lactic acid can be converted (as lactate) to pyruvate, the former in the peroxisome and the latter in the mitochondria (Lajus, et al., 2020). In fact, the undissociated form of this compound, analogous to formic and acetic acids, may inhibit the yeast growth particularly when present together with acetic acid (Narendranath, Thomas, & Ingledew, 2001). However, considering its pK_a value of 3.86 at 20 °C (O'Neil, 2013), which is even below the pK_a

of acetic acid, and the pH of the media which never reached values below 4.69 during the cultivations, the majority of this compound remained in the lactate form.

In agreement with the behaviour shown in synthetic medium, also in CSH medium the yeasts *R. toruloides* and *T. oleaginosus* exhibited a negligible or inexistent lag phase, given the good linear regression obtained through the first points of the growth curves which indicates that the cultures started by the exponential growth phases, followed by the deceleration phases, with durations of approximately 24 h in both cases, for the two yeasts. However, a decline in $\mu_{\max}$ values was observed in both yeasts to about half of the value in synthetic medium, with *T. oleaginosus* standing out from a $\mu_{\max}$ of $0.125 \pm 0.000 \text{ h}^{-1}$ to $0.054 \pm 0.001 \text{ h}^{-1}$, being even lower than *R. babjevae* that showed a $\mu_{\max}$ of $0.062 \pm 0.005 \text{ h}^{-1}$, although *R. babjevae* showed a long latency phase with more than 42 h duration. In this sense, it should be noted that the initial $OD_{600 \text{ nm}}$ on CSH medium was around 5 in all strains, while in synthetic medium it was about 2. Some authors had argued that higher initial $OD_{600 \text{ nm}}$ values increase the initial tolerance of microorganisms against inhibitors allowing to shorten the lag phase and contributing to the reproducibility of the experiments (Brandenburg, et al., 2021). In particular, *R. babjevae* DBVPG 8058 had already been grown on non-detoxified wheat straw hydrolysate with an initial $OD_{600 \text{ nm}}$ of 5 by the same authors and showed no apparent lag phase (Brandenburg, et al., 2021), which makes this observation even more unexpected. diau phenolic compounds that may inhibit these strains, since previous studies have evidenced that these compounds are detrimental to cell growth, by promoting partition and loss of integrity of cell membranes (Zhao, Peng, Du, Liu, & Liu, 2012; Silva, et al., 2021). Likewise to the synthetic medium, also on CSH medium, *R. babjevae* entered in stationary phase soon after the end of the exponential phase. Still, it should be noted that in this case the pH of the medium never reached values below 4.69 which excludes the possibility of inhibition by formic acid, but does not exclude the inhibition by other acids not quantified as propionic acid with a pK_a of 4.88 at 25 °C (Serjeant & B., 1979). The hypotheses of nutrient depletion or inhibition by a product of primary metabolism also remain on the table.

With respect to the substrates uptake profiles few differences were found. However, lactic acid, which was not studied in synthetic medium, was, in this case, consumed (as lactate) simultaneously with the other substrates by the three strains. It should be noted that among the three studied yeasts, *T. oleaginosus* presented the highest value of $-r_{\text{lactic acid,max}}$ of $0.03 \pm 0.00 \text{ g/L/h}$ parallelly to the highest percentage of assimilation of this substrate, as already highlighted, which encourages future work about the cultivation of this strain on lactate-rich effluents. Besides, it is interesting to note that xylose consumption was more substantial for residual glucose concentrations lower than 20 g/L for the two yeasts *R. toruloides* and *T. oleaginosus*, something similar to what previous studies had already reported for *T. oleaginosus* DSM 11815 (i Nogué, et al., 2018) and for *R. toruloides* CBS 14 (Brandenburg, et al., 2021).

Curiously, it was observed that in the complex hydrolysate xylose was faster consumed by the same two yeasts, being necessary only 47.1 h for its consumption to reach percentages of 84 % and 98 %, for *R. toruloides* and *T. oleaginosus*, respectively, while on synthetic medium the former strain took 95.8 h to consume 76 % of

the initial xylose concentration, and the later strain took 70.6 h to consume 93 % of the initial xylose concentration. These results are also supported by the residual xylose concentration profiles, nevertheless, no plausible explanation was found. Moreover, previous studies also performed on CSH for the yeasts *T. oleaginosus* DSM 11815 and four different strains of *R. toruloides* (Y 27012, Y 27013, DSM 4444 and DSM 70398) in shake flasks showed that $-r_{xylose,max}$ only attained values lower than 0.5 g/L/h for these microorganisms (i Nogué, et al., 2018), contrary to the $-r_{xylose,max}$ values higher than 0.9 g/L/h achieved in the present work. According also to the same study, all strains of *R. toruloides* showed a $-r_{glucose,max}$ lower than 1 g/L/h (i Nogué, et al., 2018), in contrast to the present work where *R. toruloides* showed a $-r_{glucose,max}$ of 1.12 ± 0.09 g/L/h, while *T. oleaginosus* DSM 11815 stood out as the fastest to consume glucose with a $-r_{glucose,max}$ of 1.23 g/L/h (i Nogué, et al., 2018), comparable to the 1.37 ± 0.05 g/L/h obtained in the present work. However, such differences in the results could be due to the effective sugar concentration which is much higher in the cited publication (100 g/L of total sugars compared to about 60 g/L in the present work), which might, for example, inhibit the yeasts by the substrate (i Nogué, et al., 2018).

Notably, the yeasts *R. toruloides* and *T. oleaginosus* growth were optimized when cultivated in CSH medium, comparing with the synthetic medium, since the cultivation periods were shortened from 98 h and 72 h, respectively, to only 41.7 h still achieving high DCW values of 20.34 ± 0.81 g_{DCW}/L and 27.48 ± 0.58 g_{DCW}/L, by the same order. As a consequence, noteworthy global biomass volumetric productivities of 0.339 ± 0.021 g_{DCW}/L/h and 0.488 ± 0.016 g_{DCW}/L/h were reached, values even higher than those previously obtained for *T. oleaginosus* DSM 11815 and *R. toruloides* DSM 4444 on CSH medium in a 500 mL-bioreactor with a longer cultivation period of 120 h (i Nogué, et al., 2018), or than the 0.118 ± 0.004 g_{DCW}/L/h recorded for *T. oleaginosus* DSM 11815 on CSH in another study (Gong, et al., 2016). On the contrary, the global biomass volumetric productivity for *R. babjevae* was negatively affected on CSH medium due to the long lag phase, even despite of the slightly higher DCW attained on this medium, decreasing from 0.128 ± 0.006 g_{DCW}/L/h attained on synthetic medium, to 0.085 ± 0.025 g_{DCW}/L/h observed for CSH medium, well below the DCW concentration of 0.292 ± 0.024 g_{DCW}/L/h previously reported for the same strain on wheat straw hydrolysate (Brandenburg, et al., 2021), which makes the selection of this yeast strain for this process unviable and reinforces the need for further studies with the aim at understanding the sources of its unsuccessful growth.

Finally, compared with the synthetic medium, the $Y_{X/S}$ parameters slightly increased for the two *Rhodotorula* yeasts and decreased for *T. oleaginosus*, when grown on CSH. In particular, a similar value of 0.37 ± 0.03 g_{DCW}/g had already been observed for the same strain of *T. oleaginosus* developed on CSH medium (i Nogué, et al., 2018).

4.2.2. Intracellular lipids accumulation

The mass contents of Total FAs and Total Lipids, on a DCW basis, and the respective titres in the final culture broth, in g/L, for cultures on complex CSH + CSL medium are disposed in the **Figure 22**.

Figure 22. Comparison of Total FAs and Lipids contents, in % w/w of DCW, and its titres, in g/L, at the final instants of cultivation among the three studied yeast strains: *R. toruloides* (at 30 °C), *T. oleaginosus* (at 30 °C) and *R. babjevae* (at 25 °C) grown on complex CSH + CSL medium, at a scale of 150 mL.

Based on the growth and substrates uptake profiles, and the data shown in previous figure, it was possible to obtain the kinetic parameters for the intracellular lipid accumulation for the three studied yeast strains grown on complex CSH + CSL medium, as shown in **Table 8**.

Table 8. Comparison of intracellular lipids accumulation kinetic parameters among the three studied yeast strains: *R. toruloides* (at 30 °C), *T. oleaginosus* (at 30 °C) and *R. babjevae* (at 25 °C) grown on complex CSH + CSL medium, at a scale of 150 mL.

Parameter	Unit.	<i>R. toruloides</i>	<i>T. oleaginosus</i>	<i>R. babjevae</i>
Cultivation period	h	47.1	47.1	88.9
$\text{Prod}_{\text{vol}}(\text{FAs})_{\text{global}}$	$\text{g}_{\text{FAs}}/\text{L}/\text{h}$	0.034 ± 0.003	0.106 ± 0.006	0.008 ± 0.001
$\text{Prod}_{\text{vol}}(\text{L})_{\text{global}}$	$\text{g}_L/\text{L}/\text{h}$	0.043 ± 0.005	0.144 ± 0.004	0.024 ± 0.003
$Y_{\text{FAs}/s}$	$\text{g}_{\text{FAs}}/\text{g}$	0.028 ± 0.000	0.084 ± 0.000	0.027 ± 0.000
$Y_{L/s}$	g_L/g	0.036 ± 0.001	0.114 ± 0.002	0.080 ± 0.004

FAs profiles were also obtained, allowing the calculation of the SFA, MUFA and PUFA contents, as displayed in **Figure 23**.

Figure 23. Comparison of FAs profiles, in % w/w of Total FAs, and the SFA, MUFA and PUFA contents, in % w/w of Total FAs, at the final instants of cultivation among the three studied yeast strains: *R. toruloides* (at 30 °C), *T. oleaginosus* (at 30 °C) and *R. babjevae* (at 25 °C) grown on complex CSH + CSL medium, at a scale of 150 mL.

Concerning the FAs and lipids mass contents and titres obtained on complex CSH + CSL medium, the differences from those obtained on synthetic medium for *R. toruloides* are remarkable, which unexpectedly showed unpromising results similarly to *R. babjevae*, both accumulating less than 20 % of their DCW in lipids, i.e. below the reference value for any oleaginous microorganism (Ratledge & Wynn, 2002). Among the studied yeasts on complex medium, *T. oleaginosus* generated the best results in terms of lipids accumulating, in % w/w of DCW, 18.1 ± 0.6 % w/w in total FAs and 24.6 ± 0.1 % w/w in lipids, corresponding to titres of 5.0 ± 0.3 g_{FAs}/L and 6.8 ± 0.2 g_L/L, respectively, values slightly lower than those obtained on synthetic medium. Although reasonable, these results are well below the FAs content of 63.1 ± 3.7 % w/w, corresponding to a titre of 21.4 ± 3.6 g_{FAs}/L, previously reported by i Nogué, et al. (2018). This difference could be explained, among other factors, by the fact that the cited work refers to a culture in a 500 mL STR-bioreactor, which shows better aeration and mixing efficiencies than the Erlenmeyer flasks, in addition, the higher initial concentration of sugars, of around 100 g/L, much higher than the 60 g/L of total sugars present in the CSH used in the present work, or even with the use of 2 g/L yeast extract, 4 g/L peptone and 1.6 g/L YNB as supplements instead of the CSL and the defined mineral medium used in the present work may explain the higher lipid production by this strain, reported by (i Nogué, et al., 2018). Some *R. toruloides* strains such as Y4 and DSM 4444 had also been studied in CSH producing, respectively, a total lipids content of 36.4 % w/w, for a titre of 5.53 g_L/L (Xie, et al., 2012), and a total FAs content of 60.8 ± 1.1 % w/w of DCW, for a titre of 23.3 ± 1.8 g_{FAs}/L (i Nogué, et al., 2018), largely above to

those obtained for *R. toruloides* strain used in this study. No literature was found reporting the growth of *R. babjevae* DBVPG 8058 on CSH medium, however, as already mentioned, an extraordinary performance has been already observed on WSH (Brandenburg, et al., 2021), i.e. with a composition quite similar to that of the present work, so, in principle this was not the reason for the poor results, as already discussed.

The total lipid content for *R. babjevae* cultivated on CSH was more than three times its total FAs content. On synthetic medium the ratio between the total lipids and FAs contents was already relatively higher comparing to the other yeasts, but it was never twice as high. A possible explanation for this fact could be the accumulation of high amounts of other lipids instead of TAGs, such as torularhodin or torulene, both carotenoids commonly produced by yeasts from the *Rhodotorula* or *Rhodospiridium* genus (Peng, Fakankun, & Levin, 2021). Additionally, to elucidate this question, lipid fractionation methods would be necessary to determine the lipid profiles.

In terms of global volumetric productivities of total lipids and FAs, the results differ significantly from those obtained for the synthetic medium, and in the case of *R. toruloides* these parameters dropped by about half when the yeast was grown on CSH even considering the increase in biomass production, which could, for example, be explained in a scenario of a lower C:N ratio for the CSH medium. In fact, estimating the molar C:N ratios by calculation (not obtained experimentally) it can be observed that this parameter was meaningfully higher for the synthetic medium (39.4) against the 6.8 for the complex medium. Indeed, although the optimal C:N ratio that optimises lipids and FAs productivities varies from strain to strain, it is known that higher C:N values usually lead to higher lipids and FAs and contents (Calvey C. , Su, Willis, McGee, & Jeffries, 2016), still, experimental nitrogen determinations would be needed to support this hypothesis. In contrast, *T. oleaginosus* performance did not show significant differences on synthetic medium, with equally promising values of $0.106 \pm 0.006 \text{ g}_{\text{FAs}}/\text{L}/\text{h}$ and $0.144 \pm 0.004 \text{ g}_\text{L}/\text{L}/\text{h}$, the former slightly lower and the latter a bit higher. Although, these values remained lower than the $0.22 \pm 0.03 \text{ g}_{\text{FAs}}/\text{L}/\text{h}$ (i Nogué, et al., 2018) and the $0.195 \text{ g}_\text{L}/\text{L}/\text{h}$ (Gong, et al., 2014) previously obtained for the same strain also cultivated on CSH, which provides an opportunity to further work on the optimization and scale-up of this strain.

Concerning the FAs profiles obtained for each strain, comparing them to those observed for the synthetic medium, it is possible to conclude that both *Rhodotorula* strains presented a higher degree of unsaturation when cultivated in CSH, which can be partly explained due to the fact that the culture was harvested earlier, i.e. only 24 h after the end of the exponential growth phase, taking into account that previous studies for several oleaginous yeasts, among which *R. toruloides* DSM 4444 or *T. oleaginosus* DSM 11815, show that the SFA content tends to increase over the cultivation time as a consequence of the decrease in activity of the desaturase enzymes Δ -12 and Δ -9 (i Nogué, et al., 2018). However, this purpose is not in agreement with the high degree of saturation found in *T. oleaginosus* on CSH, with an SFA content of $48.9 \pm 0.0 \%$, the highest quantified in the present work, even though the culture was harvested earlier.

For a more detailed analysis, some FAs profiles collected for the same strain together with those obtained on CSH and synthetic media in the present work were summarized in **Table 9**.

Table 9. Comparison of major FAs profiles, obtained in the present study and collected from different literature for *T. oleaginosus* strains.

Medium	C 14:0	C 16:0	C 18:0	C 18:1 ω-9	C 18:2 ω-6	Reference
	% w/w of Total FAs					
Synthetic	0.9 ± 0.0	29.1 ± 0.0	11.4 ± 0.0	48.3 ± 0.1	7.1 ± 0.0	This work
CSH + CSL	1.8 ± 0.0	28.0 ± 0.0	14.8 ± 0.0	41.9 ± 0.0	7.5 ± 0.0	This work
CSH	0.8 ± 0.0	27.8 ± 0.2	14.8 ± 0.3	43.0 ± 0.4	7.5 ± 0.1	(Gong, et al., 2016)
CSH	1.2 ± 0.1	29.4 ± 0.7	18.4 ± 0.5	44.1 ± 2.3	1.5 ± 0.3	(Gong, et al., 2014)
WSH + CSL	u.i.	23.5 ± 0.6	13.6 ± 0.3	55.2 ± 0.6	7.3 ± 0.1	(Shaigani, et al., 2021)
WSH	u.i.	25.9 ± 0.0	15.2 ± 0.2	47.7 ± 0.3	6.4 ± 0.1	(Yu, Zheng, Dorgan, & Chen, 2011)

u.i. – unavailable information

In view of the major FAs profiles collected from the literature for the selected strain, few differences can be pointed out to the results in the present work, and the high SFA contents seem to be an intrinsic phenotypic characteristic, therefore, little dependent on the culture conditions and/or the medium used. Nevertheless, the culture strategy (simultaneous saccharification, separate hydrolysis, enhanced lipid synthesis, etc.), the composition of the culture medium (carbon sources, inhibitors present, nutrient ratio, etc.), the metabolic phase of the yeast (exponential growth, deceleration, stationary, etc.), cultivation mode (batch, fed-batch, continuous) and operational parameters (stirring, aeration, pH, temperature, etc.), could explain the subtle differences found between different publications (Gong, et al., 2014; Yu, Zheng, Dorgan, & Chen, 2011; i Nogué, et al., 2018; Rossi, et al., 2009).

4.3. Lab-scale bioreactor experiment

After the previous screening step for the selection of the best yeast strain, in terms of lipid production, further experiments were conducted in a 7 L-bioreactor. However, firstly, a preliminary analysis of some challenges and relevant aspects to be considered was made, before describing the bioreactor experiments.

4.3.1. Preliminary considerations

Taking into consideration that the performance of a fermentation depends heavily on fluid hydrodynamics and mass and heat transfer phenomena in the cultivation vessel, in addition to the intrinsic biological properties, scale-up is usually a major challenge in biotechnology, and oxygen transfer is often the limiting step to the optimal performance of aerobic processes (Fonseca & Teixeira, 2007) since, unlike most of the nutrients, oxygen has a low solubility in water. Thus, the strategy for a good oxygen supply in a bioreactor is usually to maximise the gas-liquid interfacial area and residence time of air bubbles in the medium, which can be achieved, for instance, with an efficient agitation, so that bubbles may be broken up into smaller ones (as small as possible) and uniformly dispersed throughout the broth, being the stirring speed and the impeller design a crucial key (Humbird & Fei, 2016). However, too high stirring speeds largely contribute to increased energy costs. It is even estimated that the oxygen transfer supply can reach 15 to 20 % of the overall operating costs in aerobic processes (Zhong, 2011). In addition to these issues, increased aeration strongly contributes to the phenomenon of foam formation in the bioreactor, together with the properties of the medium, namely, the protein content or the presence of surface-active molecules (Delvigne & Lecomte, 2010).

It should be noted that *T. oleaginosus* cultivations foamed the most among the experiments represented in sections 4.1 and 4.2, a phenomenon that seemed to be intensified in the medium containing hydrolysate, as shown in the **Figure 24**, most likely due to the addition of hydrolytic enzymes during CS enzymatic hydrolysis step and the supplementation of the medium with CSL. Thus, according to the previous line of thought, foaming would be expected to represent one of the main limitations to scale-up to this strain.

Figure 24. Foaming phenomenon for *T. oleaginosus* cultures developed in 1 L-Erlenmeyer flasks with 150 mL volume of culture medium: a) semi-defined synthetic medium; b) CSH + CSL complex medium.

Regarding this phenomenon, *R. babjevae*, when grown at 25 °C either on CSH-mimic synthetic medium or on CSH + CSL complex medium, stood out by its anti-foaming properties, as no foaming was observed, as shown in the **Figure 25**, even during the 120-rpm agitation.

Figure 25. Observed foaming / anti-foaming responses of *R. babjevae* under different conditions: a) at 30 °C on CSH-mimic synthetic medium; b) at 25 °C on CSH-mimic synthetic medium; c) at 25 °C on CSH+CSL complex medium.

In fact, previous studies have reported the production of PEFA, extracellular glycolipids, by various yeasts of the genus *Rhodotorula* or *Rhodosporidium*, under high C:N ratios, including *R. babjevae* sp. (Garay, et al., 2017; Sandberg, 2019). It is known that this group of amphipathic molecules present biosurfactant characteristics, promoting a decrease in the surface tension of the media to values comparable to commercial anti-foaming agents (Wang, et al., 2019). Besides their surface activity, these PEFA could also be of commercial interest for their antifungal, antibacterial, antiviral, and anti-carcinogenic properties (Sandberg, 2019).

Considering the presence of inhibitory compounds in CSH, such as HMF or furfural, which are known to affect the cells physiological state, and the presence of appreciable amounts of suspended solids in this complex residual medium, a strategy of double-staining SGI and PI coupled to FC was used, during *T. oleaginosus* cultivations conducted in the 7 L-bioreactor. Firstly, aiming at identifying specific populations for further comparison with the results obtained during fermentations, via FC, preliminary control tests were performed using the oleaginous yeast *T. oleaginosus* cultivated on YPD medium for 24 h, under extreme physiological conditions, namely, live cells taken from an exponential phase growing culture, therefore with mostly intact membranes, and heat-killed cells in boiling water for 30 min, with injured membranes. No-staining, which is assumed as cells autofluorescence, and stained cells with 2 μ L of SGI and 1 μ L of PI, for 15 min, were run. The cytograms (density plots) concerning these analyses are shown in **Figure 26**.

Staining: SGI (2 μ L) + PI (1 μ L) for 15 min

Figure 26. Preliminary FC control trials for *T. oleaginosus* sub-population identification, shown in density plots of SGI fluorescence versus PI fluorescence: by running in flow cytometer unstained exponential phase growing cells (a) and heat-killed cells (b), and by running stained exponential growing cells (c) and heat-killed cells (d) with SGI (2 μ L) and PI (1 μ L) for 15 min: Population A - Cells with intact membranes [SGI+; PI-]; Population B - Cells with injured membranes [SGI+; PI+].

SGI staining was not efficient enough, thus, not allowing a total displacement of population A from the bottom left quadrant to the upper left quadrant of the cytogram. It should be reminded that when using media containing many solid residues, as in lignocellulosic hydrolysates, a cell-specific staining is necessary, such as the SGI employed in the present work.

Figure 26 has already demonstrated that heat-killed cells stained with SGI and PI resulted in an unquestionable increase in signal from both detectors, contrarily to exponential phase growing cells. In fact, there are several factors that can affect the staining rates and efficiencies, such as temperature, incubation time or fluorochromes concentrations (Nescerecka, Hammes, & Juhna, 2016), raising suspicions about a protocol unsuitable to this yeast strain. However, no publications were found regarding SGI staining protocols for *T. oleaginosus*.

Along these lines, an optimisation of the staining protocol for *T. oleaginosus* was proposed, by simultaneously testing increasing SGI concentrations from 2 to 3 μ L and staining times from 15 to 30 min, and the resulting cytograms are depicted in **Figure 27**. Note that PI concentration was kept constant, and since only the SGI concentration and incubation time were optimised, the density plots in **Figure 27** show SGI fluorescence versus SSC (cell internal complexity), instead of PI fluorescence, as previously shown in **Figure 26**.

Figure 27. Optimisation trials of the staining protocol for *T. oleaginosus* cultivated on CSH-mimic synthetic medium for different dye concentrations and staining times, shown in density plots of SGI fluorescence versus SSC (cell internal complexity): a) Exponential growing cells stained with SGI (2 μ L) and PI (1 μ L) for 15 min; b) Exponential growing cells stained with SGI (2 μ L) and PI (1 μ L) for 30 min; c) Exponential growing cells stained with SGI (3 μ L) and PI (1 μ L) for 15 min; d) Exponential growing cells stained with SGI (3 μ L) and PI (1 μ L) for 30 min;

In general, both an increase in SGI concentration and staining time resulted in a higher intensity of the SGI signal detected in FITC, leading to a better identification of population A, something that had already been demonstrated for porcine immune cells within certain limits (Briggs & Jones, 2005). Nevertheless, the effect of these two variables on FITC signal intensity was not linear, whereby fixing the dosage of 2 μ L of SGI, an increase in staining time from 15 to 30 min resulted in an increase from 85.19 % to 92.09 % of the fraction of events counted as SGI+, whereas fixing the dosage of 3 μ L of SGI, an increase in staining time from 15 to 30 min only contributed to an increase from 92.27 % to 95.28 % of this fraction.

Thus, the problem of the initial low fluorescence of *T. oleaginosus* cells double-stained with SGI and PI was solved by increasing SGI concentration and incubation time. In view of this conclusions, the staining with 3 μ L of SGI and 1 μ L for 30 min was adopted for all subsequent experiments.

4.3.2. Growth and substrates uptake

Once *T. oleaginosus* was selected as the oleaginous strain with best performance in terms of lipid production when grown on CSH + CSL medium, it was firstly cultivated on 2 L of CSH-mimic synthetic semi-defined medium supplemented with CSL and mineral medium in a 7 L-bioreactor (STR), aiming to optimise an environmentally sustainable bioprocess for microbial lipid production, for future scale-up at 100 L pilot scale. The growth and substrates uptake profiles as well as the stirring speed and DO parameters recorded over the cultivation time are thus represented in **Figure 28**.

Figure 28. Residual sugars and inhibitors concentration, $OD_{600\text{ nm}}$, and DCW concentration (a), and stirring rate and DO (b) profiles for *T. oleaginosus* (at 30 °C, pH 5.5, 1 vvm) recorded during cultivation on 2 L of CSH-mimic synthetic semi-defined medium, in a 7 L-STR. Note: the dashed line drawn at 51.7 h represents the instant of addition of 50 mL of a concentrated glucose (409 g/L) and xylose (204 g/L) pulse.

Hence, the growth curve for the above cultivation was plotted as the variation of the Napierian logarithm of the DCW with the incubation time and represented in the **Figure 29**.

Figure 29. Napierian logarithm of biomass concentration versus time profile for *T. oleaginosus* cultivation at 30 °C, pH 5.5, and 1 vvm, on 2 L of CSH-mimic synthetic semi-defined medium, in a 7 L-STR. Calculation of the μ_1 and μ_2 parameters. Note: the line drawn at 51.7 h represents the instant of addition of 50 mL of a concentrated glucose (409 g/L) and xylose (204 g/L) pulse.

As expected, no lag-phase was detected, although it should be noted that the initial $OD_{600\text{ nm}}$ was the lowest quantified in the present work, of around 1.5 compared to about 2.1 and 4.8 recorded for CSH-mimic semi-defined synthetic medium (4.1) and CSH + CSL complex medium (4.2), respectively, at a scale of 150 mL, highlighting the growth robustness of this yeast. Three growth phases could be detected during this experiment: a first growth phase (from $t = 0\text{ h}$ to $t = 19.7\text{ h}$) with a μ_1 of 0.121 h^{-1} ; a second growth phase (from $t = 19.7\text{ h}$ to $t = 51.7\text{ h}$) with a μ_2 (0.029 h^{-1}), lower than the μ_1 , and a death phase (from $t = 51.7\text{ h}$ to $t = 68.2\text{ h}$), during which the biomass concentration decreased from $11.7 \pm 0.2\text{ g/L}$ to $6.5 \pm 0.0\text{ g/L}$. The first μ was slightly lower than the 0.125 h^{-1} obtained in 4.1. At first sight, it could also be explained with the oxygen limitation confirmed during the whole process, as noticed above, since previous studies have already shown that oxygen-limiting conditions can negatively affect the biomass growth for *T. oleaginosus* DSM 11815 (Zhang, et al., 2018; Davies, Holdsworth, & Reader, 1990).

The FC analysis performed for two instants comprised within the second growth phase (25.9 and 48.0 h) and another at the end of fermentation, i.e., during the death phase (68.2 h), were obtained and represented in

Figure 30.

Figure 30. FC analysis for the second growth phase (25.9 h and 48.0 h) and death phase (68.2 h) *T. oleaginosus* (at 30 °C, pH 5.5, 1 vvm) cultivated on 2 L of CSH-mimic synthetic semi-defined medium, in a 7 L-STR. Note that the represented cytograms correspond to one of the three technical replicates run in flow cytometer.

Once the PC5.5-FITC and SSC-FSC (x-y coordinate) cytograms were obtained, the upper left (Q1-UL) and upper right (Q1-UR) quadrants of the PC5.5-FITC cytogram were defined, by comparison with the control assays, corresponding to the events stained with SGI but not with PI [SGI+; PI-]. Since these events are stained with SGI, but not with PI, they are considered cells with intact membrane. The events double-stained with SGI and PI [SGI+; PI+] are considered cells with compromised membranes. Intuitively, the joining of the quadrants Q1-UL and Q1-UR corresponds to the totality of the events stained with SGI, as being the total cells in the culture, at the harvesting moment. Quadrant either Q1-UL or Q1-UR could still be isolated in SSC-FSC cytograms, being feasible to follow the evolution of relative cell size and intracellular complexity all over the culture, for cells with intact or compromised membranes, respectively.

Table 10. Concentration of events for each quadrant Q1-UL and Q1-UR and the union of both, obtained via FC analysis, for the second growth phase (t = 25.9 h and t = 48.0 h) and death phase (68.2 h) for *T. oleaginosus* (at 30 °C, pH 5.5, 1 vvm) cultivated on 2 L of CSH-mimic synthetic semi-defined medium, in a 7 L-STR.

Quadrant	Population	Unit.	25.9 h	48.0 h	68.2 h
Q1-UL [SGI+;PI-]	Cells with intact membrane	10 ⁸ events/mL	4.92 ± 0.52 (91.9 %)	7.99 ± 0.96 (94.6 %)	3.67 ± 0.12 (74.3 %)
Q1-UR [SGI+;PI+]	Cells with permeabilised membrane	10 ⁸ events/mL	0.43 ± 0.02 (8.1 %)	0.45 ± 0.05 (5.4 %)	1.27 ± 0.16 (25.7 %)
Q1-UL + Q1-UR [SGI+]	Sum of both sub-populations	10 ⁸ events/mL	5.35 ± 0.54	8.44 ± 1.01	4.93 ± 0.23

Unfortunately, between the moment of addition of 50 mL of the concentrated carbon solution and the last sampling point, an uncontrolled foaming event was recorded resulting in the loss of a large part of the culture broth through the bioreactor air-outlet (**Figure 31**), parallelly to an abnormal depletion of the HCl and NaOH 2.5 M solutions, being an estimated volume of about 1 L of both solutions added to the bioreactor vessel (**Figure 31**).

Figure 31. Uncontrolled foaming episode, which occurred between 51.7 and 68.2 h, with emphasis on significant loss of volume of broth through the bioreactor air outlet (to the left of the bioreactor) and on acid and base depletion (to the right of the bioreactor).

Because of these two events, a significant loss of cells carried away by the foam and a dilution of soluble nutrients predictably occurred, which invalidates the majority of results from 51.7 hours onwards. Thus, the results presented henceforth refer mainly to the fermentation in batch mode only (ending at 51.4), since the overall fermentation (ending at 68.2 h) is not reproducible.

The growth and substrates uptake kinetic parameters for the 2 L-fermentation were calculated and depicted in the **Table 11**.

Table 11. Growth and substrates uptake kinetic parameters for *T. oleaginosus* (at 30 °C, pH 5.5, 1 vvm) cultivated on 2 L of CSH-mimic synthetic semi-defined medium, in a 7 L-bioreactor (STR). Note that the parameters regarding the overall fermentation were discarded given the culture loss and accidental dilution.

Parameter	Unit.	Until the pulse
Sample instant	h	51.4
Stirring speed range	rpm	100 - 220
PPG 425 added	μL	391.5
Initial C:N molar ratio	mol/mol	17.2
Growth kinetic parameters:		
X_{DCW} max	g _{DCW} /L	12.00 ± 0.33 (51.4 h)
X_{DCW} final	g _{DCW} /L	12.00 ± 0.33
Prod_{vol}(X_{DCW})_{global}	g _{DCW} /L /h	0.225 ± 0.010
Prod_{vol}(X_{DCW})_{max.}	g _{DCW} /L /h	0.225 ± 0.010

μ_1	h^{-1}	0.121
μ_2	h^{-1}	0.029
$Y_{X/S}$	g_{DCW}/g	0.404 ± 0.010
Substrates uptake kinetic parameters:		
$-r_{Glucose,max}$	$g/L/h$	0.87 ± 0.12
$-r_{Xylose,max}$	$g/L/h$	0.26 ± 0.08
$-r_{Acetic\ acid,max}$	$g/L/h$	0.10 ± 0.00
$-r_{Formic\ acid,max}$	$g/L/h$	0.04 ± 0.00
$-r_{Lactic\ acid,max}$	$g/L/h$	0.01 ± 0.01
$-r_{Glucose,global}$	$g/L/h$	0.49 ± 0.01
$-r_{Xylose,global}$	$g/L/h$	0.07 ± 0.00
$-r_{Acetic\ acid,global}$	$g/L/h$	0.05 ± 0.00
$-r_{Formic\ acid,global}$	$g/L/h$	0.02 ± 0.00
$-r_{Lactic\ acid,global}$	$g/L/h$	0.01 ± 0.00

Looking firstly at the growth and substrates uptake profiles, it is noticeable that the DCW curve did not match the $OD_{600\ nm}$ curve (**Figure 28**), as such no valid correlation was obtained, contrary to the *T. oleaginosus* cultivations conducted in shake-flasks, in both 4.1 and 4.2 sections (see **Appendix II**). This observation was not surprising, since it is known that the relationship between these two measurements is usually not linear in bioreactors, and parallel experiments are often needed to obtain a more accurate correlation, comprising process variations over the incubation time (Luong & Male, 2011). At first glance, a possible explanation could be the variation of the culture medium itself by clarification / opacification and precipitation / solubilisation, since one of the assumptions of OD and DCW methods is that the culture medium maintains the same turbidity and solids content, correspondingly, over the cultivation time. On the other hand, as can be seen from **Figure 28**, cultivation was performed mostly under oxygen-limiting conditions, with the DO sensor registering values around 0 % of saturation from $t = 3.0$ h onwards.

Oxygen-limiting conditions led the cells to experience adverse conditions, such that their size, density, opacity, or granularity may have been affected, thus altering the correlation between cell weight and light scattering by the cells (Chioccioli, Hankamer, & Ross, 2014). This observation still reinforces the importance of using other methods for cell growth monitoring in bioreactors, especially for media with high solids contents, such as the measurement of proteins, DNA, RNA, ATP, or phospholipids (Fonseca & Teixeira, 2007), or even FC (Silva, Reis, Hewitt, & Roseiro), the latter also used in this work. However, because few experimental samples were collected and analysed via FC during the yeast cultivations, it was not possible to conclude the relationship

between FC data with the classical biomass quantification methods, in the present work. Anyway, although with its limitations, DCW is always considered as a reference measure for cell quantification at lab and industrial levels (Fonseca & Teixeira, 2007).

In general, the oxygen supply to the cells in an aerobic bioprocess is the result of a complex interaction between the hydrodynamics of the bioreactor, the response of the microorganism and mass transfer parameters (Tervasmäki, Latva-Kokko, Taskila, & Tanskanen, 2018). The oxygen transfer rate (*OTR*), on the one hand, is a parameter intrinsic to the cultivation conditions and depends on the global oxygen mass transfer coefficient on the liquid side, K_L , the total surface area available for oxygen mass transfer, a , and the driving force due to the difference in concentrations between the gas phase, $C_{G,Oxygen}^*$, and the liquid phase, $C_{L,Oxygen}$, i.e., $OTR = K_L a (C_{G,Oxygen}^* - C_{L,Oxygen})$ (Garcia-Ochoa, Gomez, Santos, & Merchuk, 2010; Fonseca & Teixeira, 2007).

Ideally, aeration conditions should guarantee a $C_{L,Oxygen}$ higher than its critical value for a certain microorganism, i.e., the minimum $C_{L,Oxygen}$ value that ensures that oxygen does not limit cell growth (Tervasmäki, Latva-Kokko, Taskila, & Tanskanen, 2018). The oxygen uptake rate (*OUR*), on the other hand, is related to each specific culture and depends on the specific oxygen uptake rate, q_{oxygen} , as well as the concentration of biomass X , i.e., $OUR = q_{oxygen} X$ (Garcia-Ochoa, Gomez, Santos, & Merchuk, 2010; Fonseca & Teixeira, 2007). Moreover, it is important to note that typically the oxygen requirements are not constant over time, being *OUR*, under non-limiting conditions, higher during the exponential growth phase (Garcia-Ochoa, Gomez, Santos, & Merchuk, 2010).

For a batch cultivation where $OTR = OUR$, when *OTR* is lower than the maximum theoretical *OUR* the medium becomes oxygen-limited (Fonseca & Teixeira, 2007), being this substrate in lack for the growth, maintenance and product synthesis pathways, with emphasis on the oxidative phosphorylation during aerobic respiration (Garcia-Ochoa, Gomez, Santos, & Merchuk, 2010). In this line of thought, it might be possible that this hypoxia was not so substantial at the first instants of cultivation, where the biomass concentration X as well as the oxygen requirements were lower (Garcia-Ochoa, Gomez, Santos, & Merchuk, 2010). Besides, this limitation might induce an adaptive response from the cells, altering their metabolism with time (Capusoni, et al., 2017), thus, presenting a lower specific growth rate.

Oddly, an early death phase was observed, revealed by the biomass concentration decrease (**Figure 28**) and by the proportion of 25.7 % of cells with permeabilised membranes (**Table 10**), without exhausting the carbon and nitrogen sources, and without reaching a stationary phase first. However, it should be noted that this death phase may only be apparent since it corresponds to the sum of three joint effects: i) the uncontrolled foaming with loss of a large volume of broth, as above reported; ii) the accidental dilution with about 1 L of HCl 2.5 M and NaOH 2.5 M solutions; and iii) the oxygen limitation during the whole process. In this sense, the mechanism suggested to justify this occurrence is schematised in **Figure 32**.

Figure 32. Suggested mechanism for the apparent death phase observed from the instant of addition of 50 mL of a concentrated glucose (409 g/L) and xylose (204 g/L) pulse.

Firstly, the factors behind foam formation and stabilisation are diverse and include the air entrapment in solution by air sparging and mechanical stirring, the operational conditions, such as pH or temperature, the properties of the medium, like the concentration of sugars, salts, alcohols and proteins, viscosity, ion strength or the presence of surface-active substances, as well as the development stage of the microbial culture (Guo, Wang, Wang, Wang, & Xu, 2022; Vardar-Sukan, 1992; Atri & Ashrafizadeh, 2010). In particular, the CSL present in this medium formulation is known for its high protein content, which might have contributed for foaming, by the action of agitation and pH changes. Previous studies had even reported the increase in foaming of a 20 g/L CSL solution with the decrease in pH, for pH values below 6 (Guo, Wang, Wang, Wang, & Xu, 2022), which may be related to the isoelectric point of the proteins present in this substrate. Besides, the autoclave sterilisation method has been associated to a significant increase in the foaming capacity of a protein-rich medium (Delvigne & Lecomte, 2010).

By hypothesis, when the concentrated glucose and xylose pulse was added to the culture medium, a sudden change in the properties of the medium, namely, sugar composition, pH, viscosity, ionic strength, etc., might have occurred, contributing itself to foaming formation (Guo, Wang, Wang, Wang, & Xu, 2022; Vardar-Sukan, 1992; Atri & Ashrafizadeh, 2010). Afterwards, the cells might have responded by adapting their metabolism, leading to a change in the extracellular pH or to the release of surface-active extracellular metabolites, thus, enhancing foaming mechanisms even more. Once a thick layer of foam was formed, the pH control system might also become inefficient, since each drop of acid or base added might have been retained in the liquid films of the bubbles, stimulating the pH controller to progressively add more solution, which results in consecutive cycles of excessive additions of acid and base, something that was evidenced by the unusual addition of 1 L of both solutions. Together, these events not only stimulate foaming phenomenon but also leads to the cell lysis, which in turn contributed for the severe foam formation (Vardar-Sukan, 1992). Indeed, by FC analysis, in **Table 10**, it was confirmed that, at the end of the cultivation, about 25.7 % of the cells had its membranes injured, a value significantly above the 8.1 % and 5.4 % verified at 25.9 and 48.0 h, respectively, thus confirming that this foaming episode promoted cell lysis, supporting published information (Vardar-Sukan, 1992; Atri & Ashrafizadeh, 2010).

Although this behaviour may vary between different microorganisms, previous studies for the red-yeast *Sporidiobolus pararoseus* JD-2 found that the most severe foaming occurred during the exponential growth phase (Guo, Wang, Wang, Wang, & Xu, 2022), which also coincides with the period when oxygen requirements

are typically the highest (Garcia-Ochoa, Gomez, Santos, & Merchuk, 2010). Assuming the same behaviour for *T. oleaginosus*, this may be a limitation to this process, since higher oxygen supply implies more foaming which is detrimental to the cells. Usually, antifoaming agents are used to avoid foaming during microbial cultures evolution. However, the addition of chemical antifoaming agents is associated with a decrease in $K_L a$ and consequently a decrease in *OTR* (Srivastava, Mishra, & Suresh, 2011). Thus, more detailed optimisation studies on the equilibrium between good aeration and good foaming control are required for further scale-up of this bioprocess.

Among the most used antifoaming agents there are alcohols, oils, aliphatic esters, silicone derivatives, among others (Chang, 2016). The PPG, used in the present work, is widely used in biotechnology due to its low toxicity (Fowles, Banton, & Pottenger, 2013) and high biodegradability (Zgoła-Grześkowiak, Grześkowiak, Zembrzuska, & Łukaszewski, 2006), and it is known that its hydrophobicity increases with molecular weight, such that it has been reported to become water-insoluble above 740 g/mol (Yi, Zhu, Xu, Jiang, & Zhu, 2011), thus also increasing its antifoaming effectiveness. In this line of thought, the use of analogous polymers with a higher molecular weight, for example PPG 1025 or 2000 might improve the foam control in this process.

Other possible improvements might involve mechanical or physical defoaming strategies, e.g., coupled to the turbine shaft (Delvigne & Lecomte, 2010), or even the implementation of an automated system of antifoaming solution addition. Additionally, the co-cultivation of *R. babjevae* and *T. oleaginosus* might be a promising strategy for further studies, in terms of foam self-control, preferably, without the addition of any chemical antifoaming agents, since the latter are known to have repercussions in microbial growth or in downstream processing (Delvigne & Lecomte, 2010). Additionally, the economic viability of extracting lipids from the cells during the fermentation evolution as antifoaming agents could also be explored, which by analogy with vegetable oils should be suitable for antifoaming purposes (Ifejika, Joel, & Aimikhe, 2022).

In general, this bioreactor batch cultivation proved clearly to be inefficient from the point of view of cell growth, decreasing the global and maximum biomass volumetric productivities by less than half when compared to the batch cultures in 1 L-Erlenmeyer flasks, which may be most likely due to the oxygen limitation, something that had been reported before (Broos, et al., 2022; Capusoni, et al., 2017), and also due to the uncontrolled foaming. In particular, a maximum DCW concentration, a global biomass volumetric productivity, and a $Y_{X/S}$ of 12.00 ± 0.33 g_{DCW}/L, 0.225 ± 0.010 g_{DCW}/L/h, and 0.404 ± 0.010 g_{DCW}/g, respectively, considerably above the results reported in the literature for this strain when cultivated at a bioreactor scale. For instance, a certain study, conducted in a 500 mL-bioreactor in batch mode, containing 300 mL of CSH, obtained a DCW concentration of around 33.9 g_{DCW}/L (i Nogué, et al., 2018), while other study, conducted in a 2.5 L-bioreactor with 1.2 L of cellulose fibre hydrolysate (CFH) with a carbon/salts/trace elements feeding approach, recorded a DCW concentration of 44.9 g_{DCW}/L, with corresponding global biomass volumetric productivity, and $Y_{X/S}$ values of 0.468 g_{DCW}/L/h and 0.21 g_{DCW}/g (Siebenhaller, et al., 2018). Additionally, the global and maximum volumetric rates of substrates uptake were also negatively affected, with lactic acid

standing out with a consumption of only 33 % compared to the remarkable 84 % observed in 1 L-Erlenmeyer flasks.

Indeed, under oxygen limitations, the oxidative phosphorylation step of aerobic respiration is compromised due to the deficiency of the final electron acceptor, leading to a decrease in ATP production and consequently a decline in the specific growth rate, as already referred, which also results in lower biomass volumetric productivity and DCW (Calvey C. H., Su, Willis, McGee, & Jeffries, 2016).

4.3.3. Intracellular lipids accumulation

The FAs and total lipids contents and their respective titres, as well as the FAs profiles were determined for two instants during fermentation (at 49.6 h and 68.2 h), as shown in **Figure 33**.

Figure 33. Total FAs and Lipids contents, in % w/w of DCW, and its titres, in g/L (to the left), as well as FAs profiles, in % w/w of Total FAs, and the SFA, MUFA and PUFA contents, in % w/w of Total FAs (to the right), for *T. oleaginosus* (at 30 °C, pH 5.5, 1 vvm) cultivated on 2 L of CSH-mimic synthetic semi-defined medium, in a 7 L-STR. Note that due to the small amount of biomass taken from the instant $t = 49.6$ h, it was not possible to determine the respective lipid content.

The kinetic parameters for the intracellular lipid accumulation for *T. oleaginosus* cultivated in 2 L of CSH-mimic synthetic medium, supplemented with CSL and mineral medium, in a 7 L-STR, were calculated, as shown in **Table 12**.

Table 12. Intracellular lipids accumulation kinetic parameters for *T. oleaginosus* (at 30 °C, pH 5.5, 1 vvm) cultivated on 2 L of CSH-mimic synthetic semi-defined medium, in a 7 L-STR. Note that the parameter regarding the substrates uptake for the overall fermentation was discarded given the accidental dilution.

Parameter	Unit.	49.6 h	68.2 h
Prod_{Vol}(FAs)_{global}	g _{FAs} /L/h	0.016 ± 0.001	0.012 ± 0.000
Prod_{Vol}(L)_{global}	g _L /L/h	-	0.018 ± 0.003
Y_{FAs/S}	g _{FAs} /g	0.028 ± 0.001	-

In order to optimise the process concerning the global volumetric productivity in total lipids and FAs, a fed-batch mode was proposed with the addition of a low-volume concentrated pulse of glucose and xylose. This strategy presupposes that at the beginning of fermentation the C:N ratio is low enough to maximise cell growth and after the end of the exponential growth phase it reaches a relatively high value such that it induces and prolongs the intracellular lipids accumulation phase (Hassan, Blanc, Granger, Pareilleux, & Goma, 1996). A previous study for *T. oleaginosus* DSM 11815 had already demonstrated that, comparing to the batch operation mode, a fed-batch strategy, maintaining the glucose concentration between 20 to 35 g/L throughout the cultivation, could optimise volumetric productivities in total lipids and FAs up to a maximum peak located at the end of the lipogenic phase (Hassan, Blanc, Granger, Pareilleux, & Goma, 1996). Other studies for the same yeast strain also have demonstrated the success of this operation mode with the addition of concentrated pulses of a sugar mixture (Meo, Laura Priebe, & Weuster-Botz, 2017) or with other substrates like pre-treated crude glycerol (Cui, Blackburn, & Liang, 2012). However, few papers were found reporting the simultaneous addition of glucose and xylose, which may be due to the current market price of xylose, which is about 8 times that of glucose (Yin, Cao, Jin, Xian, & Liu, 2021), making this feed formulation disadvantageous from the economic point of view and process profitability.

It should also be reinforced, in view of what has been discussed in previous sections, that the consumption of xylose for this strain occurs more significantly when glucose reaches concentrations below 20 g/L, which is in accordance with the fact that only 16 % of this sugar was consumed until the addition of the pulse, where still 19.5 ± 0.2 g/L of glucose was present. Therefore, the addition of a concentrated pulse containing both sugars or even only glucose could inhibit the consumption of the xylose naturally present in the CSH, which could consequently decrease the Y_{L/S} and Y_{FAs/S} values. Besides, as also already concluded, the fed-batch mode could have been the cause of the uncontrolled foaming episode. Thus, the key to optimise the global volumetric productivities in total lipids and FAs might reside in further improvements of the batch regime by, for instance, increase the C:N ratio, or other conditions with emphasis on the oxygen supply that limited the process.

Conversely, while oxygen limitation has been shown to be detrimental to cell growth, it should favour lipid synthesis, given the lower ATP requirements of these pathways compared to the nucleic acid and protein synthesis (Calvey C. H., Su, Willis, McGee, & Jeffries, 2016; Davies, Holdsworth, & Reader, 1990). However, this

was not observed in the present work, with a lipid mass content attaining only 14.1 ± 2.4 % of DCW, quite below the 24.6 ± 0.1 % and 25.3 ± 0.1 % recorded in the cultivations developed on CSH + CSL complex hydrolysate and CSH-mimic semi-defined synthetic medium in shake-flasks, respectively. Besides, lower lipid and FAs volumetric productivities was also obtained, with values of 0.016 ± 0.001 g_{FAs}/L/h, at the end of batch mode, or 0.018 ± 0.003 g_L/L/h and 0.012 ± 0.000 g_{FAs}/L/h, at the end of the overall experiment. Indeed, previous literature for this yeast strain grown in STR bioreactors have shown significantly higher lipid and FAs contents, as well as higher lipid and FAs volumetric productivities, giving the example of a study conducted in a 500 mL-bioreactor containing 300 mL of CSH, that recorded a FAs content of 63.1 ± 3.7 % of DCW with a corresponding FAs global volumetric productivity of 0.22 ± 0.03 g_{FAs}/L/h, as above mentioned (i Nogué, et al., 2018).

Despite of the uncontrolled foaming episode, other explanation behind this differences may lie in the C:N molar ratio, since only when the nitrogen concentration is significantly reduced the metabolic flux through the Krebs cycle slows down forcing the Acetyl-CoA to move towards the lipid synthesis pathways (Calvey C. H., Su, Willis, McGee, & Jeffries, 2016). Moreover, previous studies with *T. oleaginosus* DSM 11815 in batch mode reported the optimisation of the total lipids volumetric productivity for initial C:N molar ratios between 105 mol/mol (Awad, Bohnen, Mehlmer, & Brueck, 2019) and 207.4 mol/mol (Ivančić Šantek, Miškulin, Petrović, Beluhan, & Šantek, 2017), values much higher than the 17.2 mol/mol C:N ratio determined in the present work. Another study previously cited for the same yeast, in fed-batch mode, showed that the total lipids volumetric productivity was maximum for an instantaneous C:N of 58.3 mol/mol (Hassan, Blanc, Granger, Pareilleux, & Goma, 1996), a value comparable to the 58.4 mol/mol determined at the final instant of the global experiment. Additionally, three-dimensional models allow stating that besides the C:N ratio, also the individual amount of carbon and nitrogen available in the medium has an influence on lipid productivity (Pham, et al., 2021). Thus, further optimisation trials are suggested on the initial C:N ratios, for the case of batch mode, or alternatively on the instantaneous C:N ratios, for a fed-batch mode with two phases, a first favouring cell growth and a second favouring lipid synthesis.

Finally, few differences can be found in terms of the FAs profile determined in this experiment compared to the 1 L-Erlenmeyer experiments, though, in agreement with what has already been observed by other authors (i Nogué, et al., 2018), the degree of saturation was also proved to increase with cultivation time in this work, emphasising the decrease in the C 18:1 ω -9 and C 18:2 ω -6 fractions in favour of the increase in C 16:0 and C 18:0, as such the SFA content becomes higher than the MUFA content at the end of the overall cultivation.

5. Conclusions and Future Work

The present work provided a comparative study of three oleaginous yeasts, widely known for their ability to grow on lignocellulosic hydrolysates, in order to valorise CSH resulting from enzymatic hydrolysis preceded by pre-treatment via STEX. The primordial basis of this study, framed in the FRONTSH1P project objectives, arises from the need to treat the large quantities of corn stover residues generated after corn harvesting in countries such as Poland, where exploitation of this foodstuff shows a growing trend. In addition, this study also aimed at valorising these residues into intracellular MOs analogous to VOs, thus allowing biodegradable and bio-based products to be obtained as substitutes for fossil ones, such as lubricants and PUs, in line with the CEAP goals. However, the industrialisation of bioprocesses of this typology still presents several limitations, namely, the higher operating costs, which justifies the importance of screening the best-performing strain for this purpose, as well as optimising its cultivation conditions, aiming to develop a more productive, economically viable and environmentally sustainable bioprocess.

In this sense, firstly, the three prominent yeast strains *R. toruloides*, *R. babjevae*, and *T. oleaginosus* were cultivated on CSH-simulating synthetic medium, supplemented with YNB, at 30 °C (and 30/25 °C for *R. babjevae*), pH 5.5, and 120 rpm, at a scale of 500 mL of liquid volume, in 1 L Erlenmeyer flasks (batch mode), among which *T. oleaginosus* stood out with the highest global biomass volumetric productivity of 0.455 ± 0.006 g_{DCW}/L/h against the 0.216 ± 0.027 g_{DCW}/L/h, 0.128 ± 0.006 g_{DCW}/L/h, and 0.108 ± 0.006 g_{DCW}/L/h, for *R. toruloides*, and *R. babjevae* at 25 °C and 30 °C, respectively. Interestingly, *R. toruloides* was the one that accumulated more lipids with a lipid content of 36.2 ± 0.5 % of its DCW, comparing with the 25.3 ± 0.1 %, 20.7 ± 0.0 % and 17.8 ± 0.1 % obtained for *T. oleaginosus*, and *R. babjevae* at 30 °C and 25 °C, respectively. However, due to a higher biomass formation, *T. oleaginosus* achieved the highest lipids global volumetric productivity of 0.119 ± 0.001 g_L/L/h, in face of 0.081 ± 0.009 g_L/L/h, 0.025 ± 0.001 g_L/L/h, and 0.025 ± 0.000 g_L/L/h for *R. toruloides*, and *R. babjevae* at 25 °C and 30 °C, by this order. In particular, *R. babjevae* demonstrated a peculiar growth behaviour at both temperatures, entering the early stationary phase just after exponential growth phase (which was called as “static” behaviour) which might be due to an inhibition by a primary metabolite, a decrease in the medium pH, or a nutrient depletion. Despite of that, by lowering the temperature from 30 °C to 25 °C the growth was slightly enhanced, and parallelly the lipids accumulation was negatively affected, as well as the PUFA and MUFA contents were increased.

Afterwards, the same yeasts were cultivated on real CSH, supplemented with CSL as a low-cost nitrogen and vitamins source, maintaining all the abovementioned operating conditions (only 25 °C for *R. babjevae*), being the *T. oleaginosus* the strain that presented the best performance for all the assessed parameters, with emphasis on the remarkable biomass global volumetric productivity of 0.488 ± 0.016 g_{DCW}/L/h, instead of the 0.339 ± 0.021 g_{DCW}/L/h and the 0.085 ± 0.025 g_{DCW}/L/h of the *R. toruloides* and *R. babjevae*, respectively, and the

lipid global volumetric productivity of 0.144 ± 0.004 g_L/L/h, against the 0.043 ± 0.005 g_L/L/h and the 0.024 ± 0.003 g_L/L/h revealed by *R. toruloides* and *R. babjevae*, by the same order. A similar “static” behaviour was shown by *R. babjevae* when cultivated on CSH, leaving opened the hypothesis proposed above. Curiously, only *T. oleaginosus* accumulated more than 20 % of its DCW in lipids, more precisely, 24.6 ± 0.1 %, whereas *R. babjevae* and *R. toruloides* only accumulated 18.5 ± 0.3 % and 10.0 ± 0.8 % of their DCW in lipids, which makes *T. oleaginosus* the best choice for further bioprocess optimisation and scale-up proceedings. The CSL also demonstrated to be a viable alternative to YNB as a nitrogen source. Besides, the FAs profiles of the MOs proved to meet the requirements for biolubricants and bio-based PUs production.

Once the strain *T. oleaginosus* was selected for further development of this bioprocess, it was cultivated on CSH-mimic synthetic medium, now also supplemented with CSL, at 30 °C, and pH 5.5, at a scale of 2 L of liquid medium, in a 7 L-STR (fed-batch mode), revealing modest values of lipids and biomass global volumetric productivities of 0.053 ± 0.000 g_L/L/h and 0.225 ± 0.010 g_{DCW}/L/h, respectively, before the carbon pulse addition. Such low values might be linked to oxygen limitations. After the addition of the carbon pulse, an uncontrolled foaming episode was recorded promoting broth loss, cell lysis and pH controller failures. Moreover, the SGI and PI double-staining protocol coupled with flow-cytometry, revealed that 25.7 % of the cells lost their integrity, which demonstrated that *T. oleaginosus* cells were exposed to adverse conditions at this stage of the fermentation.

Aiming at subsequent industrialisation of this bioprocess using *T. oleaginosus*, it might be advantageous to develop more optimisation work at several levels:

- Firstly, it must be necessary to overcome the limitations induced by the foaming, through the implementation of a controlled anti-foaming agent addition system (e.g., a feedback control with foam level sensor, or a feed programmed at minimum flow rate), the use of a more efficient anti-foaming agent such as PPG 2000, or even the adoption of mechanical anti-foaming approaches coupled to the bioreactor set-up. Moreover, due to its ability to naturally synthesise PEFA, *R. babjevae* could be studied in co-cultivation with *T. oleaginosus*, granting a self-control of foam formation in a large-scale bioprocess and, therefore, the reduction of costs and efforts with the addition of external chemical anti-foaming agents.
- From a biological point of view, it is suggested a re-evaluation of the formulation of the medium, for which purpose detailed studies are required to determine the nutritional ratios C:N, C:P, C:S, etc., that maximise the productivities in lipids and FAs, in order to adjust the concentrations of salts in the mineral medium, as well as the volumetric ratio CSH: CSL: mineral medium to be used. In this same line of ideas, the dilution factor of the medium should also be reviewed, with regard to the water proportion. On the one hand, if the water fraction in the medium is decreased or removed, all the components including the carbon sources will be present in higher concentration, which could be advantageous only if the tolerability limits of this strain to the inhibitors present in the CSH are met. In a scenario where inhibitory compounds are already limiting the process, a slight increase in the water fraction could also be studied, assuming that within certain limits, the decrease in inhibitor concentration can largely compensate the decrease in sugar

concentration. To this end, studies with different dilutions will be advantageous for optimising the medium formulation.

- In order to increase the economic viability of this bioprocess, and consequently the competitiveness of the final products in the global market, in a view of a future industrialisation, some approaches could be tested, such as cultivation under non-sterile conditions aiming to mitigate energy consumption with saturated steam generation, preparation of the inoculum in CSH supplemented with CSL mitigating expenses with yeast extract, peptone and glucose, operation under optimal pH and temperature ranges instead of fixed set-points that could also minimize consumption of utilities such as cooling water or electricity and reagents such as HCl and NaOH, or even the co-cultivation of *T. oleaginosus* with a symbiotic microalgae in order to decrease the costs and efforts involved in oxygen supply and media stirring. Further, in a more advanced stage of the process scale-up, it could be studied the hypothesis of designing a biorefinery for extraction of, for instance, several proteins produced by the yeast cells, as well as to evaluate the potential of treatment and reuse of the fermentation supernatant in several points of the process, as in the enzymatic hydrolysis, as a way to minimize the water consumption.
- Finally, a detailed life cycle assessment of the entire process should be carried out, ensuring that no point in the process poses any risk to the environment, avoiding unnecessary transport as far as possible, investing in electricity from renewable sources, reutilising process water as much as possible, opting for green reagents rather than fossil-based reagents, with particular focus on organic solvents commonly used for lipid extraction step, as well as tracking all the residual outlets, promoting its proper treatment, valorisation or sale to other industries that in turn reuse it.

The present study, therefore, allowed to broaden the knowledge about the response of three oleaginous yeasts widely reported in the literature when cultivated in CSH supplemented with CSL, aiming at MOs production, as well as to encourage the scientific community to develop further work on more productive, economically viable and environmentally sustainable bioprocesses for the valorisation of lignocellulosic hydrolysates.

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Appendixes

Appendix I

List of reagents and components used in the present work.

Reagent / Medium Component	Supplier brand	Chemical formula	MW (g/mol)	Degree of purity (% w/w)	Density (g/cm ³)	Method
D(+)-Glucose monohydrate	Chem-Lab NV	C ₆ H ₁₂ O ₆ ·H ₂ O	198.17	> 99	-	Culture media
D(+)-Glucose anhydrous	Labkem	C ₆ H ₁₂ O ₆	180.16	≥ 99.5	-	HPLC
D(+)-Xylose	PanReac AppliChem	C ₅ H ₁₀ O ₅	150.13	≥ 98.5	-	Culture media
D(+)-Xylose	Sigma®	C ₅ H ₁₀ O ₅	150.13	≥ 99	-	HPLC
Peptone	Fisher BioReagents™	-	-	-	-	Culture media
MEA	HIMEDIA®	-	-	-	-	Culture media
Yeast extract powder	HIMEDIA®	-	-	-	-	Culture media
Difco™ YNB	Becton Dickinson and Company	-	-	-	-	Culture media
Glacial acetic acid	Merck	CH ₃ COOH	60.05	≥ 99.8	1.05	Culture media and HPLC
Formic acid	Chem-Lab NV	HCOOH	46.03	> 99	1.22	Culture media and HPLC
HMF	Biosynth Carbosynth	C ₆ H ₆ O ₃	126.11	> 97	-	Culture media and HPLC
2-Furaldehyde	Thermo Scientific	C ₅ H ₄ O ₂	96.08	99	1.16	Culture media and HPLC
Methanol	Merck	CH ₃ OH	32.04	≥ 99.9	-	FID-GC
Petroleum ether	CARLO ERBA Reagents	-	-	-	-	FID-GC
Acetyl chloride	Sigma-Aldrich	CH ₃ COCl	78.50	≥ 99	-	FID-GC
n-Heptane	CARLO ERBA Reagents	C ₇ H ₁₆	100.20	99	-	FID-GC
Tridecanoic acid	Nu-Chek Prep, Inc.	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₁ COOH	214.34	> 99	-	FID-GC
Compressed nitrogen	ALPHAGAZ™	N ₂	28.01	≥ 99.999	-	FID-GC and Bioreactor

n-Hexane	Honeywell	C ₆ H ₁₄	86.18	≥ 95	-	Soxhlet
Ethanol absolute	PanReac	CH ₃ CH ₂ OH	46.07	≥ 99.5	-	Kjeldahl
Concentrated sulphuric acid	Riedel-de Haën®	H ₂ SO ₄	98.08	95-97	1.84	Kjeldahl
Boric acid	PRONALAB®	H ₃ BO ₃	61.83	≥ 99.8	-	Kjeldahl
Mercury (II) oxide	Merck	HgO	216.59	≥ 99	-	Kjeldahl
Sodium thiosulphate pentahydrate	Merck	Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ ·5H ₂ O	248,18	≥ 99.999	-	Kjeldahl
Potassium sulphate	Chem-Lab NV	K ₂ SO ₄	174.27	≥ 99	-	Kjeldahl
Sodium hydroxide	PanReac	NaOH	40.00	≥ 98	-	Kjeldahl and bioreactor
Methylene blue	Chem-Lab NV	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ ClN ₃ S	319.85	≥ 96	-	Kjeldahl
Methyl red	Merck	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂	269.31	≥ 95	-	Kjeldahl
Phenolphthalein	Merck	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₄	318.33	≥ 99	-	Kjeldahl
Ammonium sulphate	PanReac AppliChem	(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	132.14	≥ 99	-	Culture media
Magnesium sulphate heptahydrate	PanReac AppliChem	MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	246.48	≥ 99.5	-	Culture media
Monopotassium phosphate	PanReac AppliChem	KH ₂ PO ₄	136.09	≥ 98	-	Culture media
PPG 425	Acros Organics	-	~ 425	-	1.00	Bioreactor
Hydrochloric acid 25 %	PanReac	HCl	36.46	25.0	1.12	Bioreactor
PBS	Oxoid	-	-	-	-	FC
SIG	Thermo Fisher Scientific	C ₃₂ H ₃₇ N ₄ S ⁺	509.73	-	-	FC
PI	Thermo Fisher Scientific	C ₂₇ H ₃₄ I ₂ N ₄	668.39	-	-	FC

Appendix II

Quadratic correlations between OD at 600 nm and DCW for *T. oleaginosus*. No valid correlation was found for the lab-scale bioreactor experiment on CSH-mimic synthetic medium supplemented with CSL and mineral medium.

Appendix III

Detailed residual concentrations of glucose, xylose, and acetic and formic acids, in parallel with the evolution of the symmetric of the respective volumetric consumption rates, $-r_{glucose}$, $-r_{xylose}$, $-r_{acetic\ acid}$ and $-r_{formic\ acid}$, for the three studied oleaginous yeast strains: *R. toruloides* (at 30 °C), *T. oleaginosus* (at 30 °C) and *R. babjevae* (at 30 and 25 °C) on CSH-mimic synthetic medium, at a scale of 150 mL.

Appendix IV

Detailed residual concentrations of glucose, xylose, and acetic and formic acids, in parallel with the evolution of the symmetric of the respective volumetric consumption rates, $-r_{glucose}$, $-r_{xylose}$, $-r_{acetic\ acid}$, $-r_{formic\ acid}$, and $-r_{lactic\ acid}$ for the three studied oleaginous yeast strains: *R. toruloides* (at 30 °C), *T. oleaginosus* (at 30 °C) and *R. babjevae* (at 25 °C) on complex CSH + CSL medium, at a scale of 150 mL.

Appendix V

Detailed residual concentrations of glucose, xylose, and acetic and formic acids, in parallel with the evolution of the symmetric of the respective volumetric consumption rates, $-r_{glucose}$, $-r_{xylose}$, $-r_{acetic\ acid}$, $-r_{formic\ acid}$, and $-r_{lactic\ acid}$ for *T. oleaginosus* (at 30 °C, pH 5.5, 1 vvm) cultivated on 2 L of CSH-mimic synthetic semi-defined medium, in a 7 L-STR, during the batch mode of operation.

